

Deliverable Report DI.1

Case study specifications & roadmap of modelling / data requirements

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¹ R= Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA =Data sets, microdata, etc.; DMP = Data management plan; ETHICS = Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY = Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER = Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

² PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R = EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C = EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S = EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

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Acronyms Listed in this Document

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathway
API	Application Programming Interface
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CS	Case study
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GO	Graphene Oxide
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IOP	Impact Outcome Pathway
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
MODA	Modelling Data (template for describing models)
PBK	Physiologically based kinetics (models)
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluorinated Substances
R&I	Research and Innovation
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
RoHS	Restriction of Hazardous Substances in Electrical and Electronic Equipment
SAS	Synthetic Amorphous Silica
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
WP	Work Package

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Contents

1 Refinement of the INSIGHT R&I Strategy	9
1.1 Introduction to INSIGHT R&I Strategy	9
1.2 Re-confirmation and updating of the INSIGHT R&I Strategy	10
2 The INSIGHT integrated SSbD framework	11
2.1 Mapping of the existing data landscape	11
2.1.1 Data landscape for social LCA	11
2.1.2 Data landscape for Transcriptomics	12
2.2 Mapping of the existing modelling landscape.....	12
2.3 Mapping of the workflows and dependencies	13
2.4 INSIGHT Data Reporting and quality Assessment	14
2.4.1 Social LCA	15
3 Initial INSIGHT Stakeholder Engagement	16
3.1 Clustering of projects (HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-21-22-23).....	16
3.2 Engagement with PARC via SynNet	16
4 The INSIGHT Case Studies	17
4.1 Overview of the INSIGHT Case Studies – goals and objectives.....	17
4.2 Case Study summaries.....	19
4.2.1 Advanced materials including 2D materials - Graphene	19
4.2.1.1 The Graphenea materials and the Graphene case study objectives.....	19
4.2.1.2 Regulatory Landscape for the Graphene case study	21
4.2.1.3 Initial results from sLCA on the GO case study	22
4.2.2 Advanced materials - Synthetic Amorphous Silica (SAS)	23
4.2.2.1 The challenges with SAS in tyres and the basis for the case study	23
4.2.2.2 SAS materials and the different synthesis routes (conventional and from renewable resources).....	25
A. Conventional Synthesis of Synthetic Amorphous Silica	25
Bio-based Synthesis of Synthetic Amorphous Silica.....	25
4.2.2.3 Regulatory Landscape for bio-based SAS materials.....	27
4.2.3 Antimicrobial coating materials.....	28
4.2.3.1 Antimicrobial materials and the case study objectives	28
4.2.3.2 Potential Solutions and Mitigation Strategies to be explored in the antimicrobial coatings case study.....	30
4.2.3.3 Regulatory Landscape for the antimicrobial coatings case study	31
4.2.4 Per- and Polyfluorinated Substances (PFAS)	33
4.2.4.1 Comprehensive Data Gathering and Assessment on PFAS	35
4.2.4.2 Goals and Expected Outcomes of the PFAS case study	36

4.2.4.3	Regulatory Landscape for the PFAS case study.....	36
4.3	Partner engagement in and support for case study development	38
4.4	Key performance indicators for the INSIGHT Case Studies.....	38
5	Use of the INSIGHT R&I Strategy throughout the project.....	40
5.1	Summary of key decisions taken to date.....	40
5.2	Alignment with the INSIGHT Data Management Plan.....	41
5.3	Next steps and documentation of Case Studies via nanopublications.....	43
6	Bibliography	45
	ANNEX A1 – Social Impact Factors and Indicators.....	A1

Table of Figures

Figure 1:	The INSIGHT Framework for integrated impact assessment and SSbD.	8
Figure 2:	Possible pipeline for omics data analysis in the INSIGHT framework.....	12
Figure 3:	The Easy-MODA Interface Workflow from Input to Output Documentation. The image captures the step-by-step process of using the Easy-MODA system, starting from data entry in the GUI, through the editing modules for physics-based and data-based models, to the final output of a harmonised MODA document. This output encapsulates the project overview and simulation details, showcasing the system's efficacy in automating and documenting materials modelling workflows represented here by a nanoparticle toxicity simulation.	14
Figure 4:	High level summary of the INSIGHT Case studies, based on the intensive process of discussion and refinement carried out during the first 5 months of the project, and the data and model collection activities of WPs 2 and 3 to understand what is available currently and what development is needed to deliver the case studies.....	17
Figure 5:	Results of social LCA at impact sub-category level, comparing GO-infused concrete with conventional concrete of equivalent strength in two lifetime extension scenarios (+30%, +50%). Unit (risk hours) calculated as the risk level (of contributing production processes) x activity variable (working hours of contributing production processes, reflecting human contribution)..	22
Figure 6:	Summary of the roles and contributions of all INSIGHT partners to the development, implementation and dissemination of INSIGHT case studies. Each case study has a lead industry and academic partner, a core set of modelling and infrastructure providing partners, and a set of support partners who provide guidance on the regulatory landscape, dissemination approaches, documentation of the case studies and so forth.....	38
Figure 7:	Nanopublications explained. (A) RDF (trig) representation of the nanopublication encoding an assertion: (activin A receptor type 2A—gene—disease association—Colorectal Cancer); (B) graphical representation of the four parts of the nanopublications with a human-readable representation of the assertion graph; (C) network of gene-disease associations created by five nanopublications. Reproduced from Giachelle et al. (2021).....	42

Table of Tables

Table 1:	Summary of challenges associated with conventional GO, which forms the basis of this case study.....	20
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Table 2: Summary of the challenges associated with conventional SAS for tyres, which forms the basis of the SAS case study	24
Table 3: Summary of the comparison between conventional and bio-based synthesis of SAS.....	24
Table 4. Summary of Problems with Safety and Sustainability of Antimicrobial Coatings.....	30
Table 5. Summary of Problems with Safety and Sustainability of PFAS.....	35

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Executive Summary

This INSIGHT project Deliverable report (D1.1) presents four chemo/nano informatics model integration case studies, that highlight the intersection of chemical and material science safety and sustainability with state of the art *in silico* approaches for social life cycle assessment, adverse outcome pathway prediction, and point of departure analysis. The case studies will be utilised to demonstrate the power of the linked and integrated informatics models, both data-driven and physics-based models, to provide a holistic view of the safety, sustainability and functionality of the materials in their respective application areas. The case studies will form a critical demonstration of the power of linking data and information into a Knowledge Graph, and utilising this to determine new insights and linkages between seemingly disparate concepts.

The INSIGHT integrated *in silico* framework will be demonstrated via case studies, each of which targets (1) a different class of chemicals or materials; (2) a different industrial application area (batteries and electronics, firefighting chemicals, antimicrobial coatings and bio-based tyre materials); (3) a different set of models and tools that will be integrated through alignment of the data inputs and outputs and the integration of the models through user-friendly workflows to address the needs of the specific case study; (4) a different aspect of the regulatory landscape such as demonstrating an improved safety profile for Registration, Evaluation and Authorisation of Chemicals (REACH), or demonstrating increased sustainability and reduced water or carbon footprints of a product or synthesis route via the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESGR); and (5) a different scientific or regulatory question that can be answered only through the innovative integration of currently disparate modelling approaches. *Thus, the achievement of the INSIGHT case studies will be evaluated based on their demonstration of the innovative integration of models and the new technical and societal insights that can be gained through this integration.*

The focus materials and areas for the case studies include: (i) graphene oxide (GO) materials for use in batteries and construction, (ii) per- and poly-fluoroalkylated substances (PFAS) for use as lubricants, (iii) bio-based Synthetic Amorphous Silica (SAS) for enhanced performance tyres, and (iv) antimicrobial coatings for a range of antifouling applications. Each case study provides an in-depth analysis of the unique properties, applications, challenges, and regulatory considerations associated with these materials, underscoring the importance of informatics in evaluating their safety and sustainability.

I. GO for Batteries/composite and construction: GO is emerging as a promising material for improving battery performance, lifespan, and efficiency material of high-energy batteries due to its exceptional electrical conductivity, large surface area, and mechanical strength. In terms of production quantities, nano-composites are important emerging materials where among others GO play a significant role. On the other hand, GO has proven to be an efficient admixture to improve the mechanical performance and the durability of cement. Among the challenges that have yet to be overcome for widespread application of GO are scalability of the production of high-quality GO at sufficient scale, and the potential toxicity and environmental impact require thorough assessment. A key question to be addressed in the GO for batteries/composites and construction case study is the impact of GO on composite material durability and recyclability. The regulatory landscape for GO-based batteries/composite and construction includes chemical safety, waste management, and environmental impact assessments within REACH and the EU Restriction of Hazardous Substances Directive (RoHS) directive.

II. PFAS for Lubricants: PFAS are widely used in lubricants due to their superior properties such as thermal stability, low friction, and resistance to degradation. Among the challenges that have yet to be overcome and which raise regulatory concerns are the environmental persistence of PFAS

molecules leading to contamination concerns, and the potential health risks from the compounds to humans and the environment. A key objective of the PFAS case study will be to evaluate the potential to replace PFAS in key applications, and development of models to address this question. Regulation of PFAS is stringent, with the EU focusing on restricting their use through the REACH regulation and the Water Framework Directive, due to their persistence and bioaccumulation potential.

III Bio-based Synthetic Amorphous Silica for Tyres: Bio-based SAS represents a sustainable alternative to conventional silica used in tyre manufacturing, and is derived from renewable resources such as agricultural waste. Key challenges relate to ensuring uniform quality comparable to conventional SAS and scaling production cost-effectively. The bio-based SAS case study will focus on documenting the Life-cycle Assessment (LCA) and social-LCA of the bio-based SAS relative to the conventional SAS. From a regulatory perspective, bio-based SAS must comply with regulations governing the use of materials in automotive products, such as the EU's End-of-Life Vehicle (ELV) Directive and various environmental standards to promote sustainable manufacturing.

IV. Antimicrobial Coatings: Antimicrobial coatings are increasingly used to prevent the growth of harmful microorganisms on surfaces, with applications spanning healthcare, food packaging, and consumer products like high frequented surfaces. Among the technical challenges to their successful deployment are the potential for microorganisms to develop resistance, the potential for toxicity and/or allergic reactions from prolonged exposure, and environmental impacts from disposal and environmental persistence of antimicrobial agents. Key questions that this case study will address include a comparison between nano-enabled antimicrobial coatings and conventional disinfectants, and the impacts of their leeching and degradation rates. The regulatory context for antimicrobial coatings is the EU Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR), which mandates rigorous testing for safety, efficacy, and environmental impact.

The informatics-driven approach, whereby different modelling approaches including social life cycle assessment will be integrated to provide a holistic view of the chemicals or materials functionality, efficacy, safety and sustainability, is the common theme cutting across the case studies. Each case study will be documented via a series of nanopublications (a declaration or assertion of a relationship, provenance information about the assertion, and the publication information) which are structured, RDF-based formats fully compatible with the principles of linked data and the semantic web. Nanopublications are considered to be components of a knowledge Graph, which is fully consistent with the INSIGHT Data Management Plan and allows INSIGHT to demonstrate leadership in the FAIRification of models, case studies and the overarching Knowledge Graph.

1 Refinement of the INSIGHT R&I Strategy

1.1 Introduction to INSIGHT R&I Strategy

The INSIGHT project will provide a novel, integrated framework for mechanistic impact assessment of chemicals and materials. This multi-layer framework consists of a data graph (WP3), a model graph (WP2) and an impact outcome pathway (IOP) graph (WP4) that predict the health, environmental, social and economic impacts of chemicals and materials, as shown in Figure 1. The three graphs will be systematically interlinked together and used for integrated impact assessment of chemicals and materials for next generation integrated safe and sustainable by design (SSbD).

Figure 1. The INSIGHT Framework for integrated impact assessment and SSbD.

Although individual models and data sets for impact assessment exist, they have never been integrated into a network structure. Thus, the individual graphs and their integration represent a novel way to approach impact assessment in a mechanistic and holistic way. Through provision of this integrated impact assessment and SSbD framework, INSIGHT will save industry money and time in developing and producing chemicals/materials and products derived from them. It will help regulators and policy makers undertake informed decision-making that improves product safety and sustainability.

The INSIGHT project aims to:

1. Develop an integrated framework for mechanistic impact assessment based on the novel concept of an **impact outcome pathway (IOP)**, defined as a mechanistic and integrated evaluation of chemicals and materials impact whereby impact outcomes are explained as the consequence of multi-step key events, extending the adverse outcome pathway (AOP) framework to impacts;
2. Provide curated and user-friendly FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data and computational models and workflows that support the development of the next generation

SSbD chemicals and materials, with a focus on user-friendliness and democratisation of access to advanced approaches without a need for programming skills;

3. Provide open, accessible and interactive guidelines, enabling end users and stakeholders to access and operate the framework. These guidelines will help stakeholders interpret the outputs and implement informed decisions compatible with the SSbD principles. This will be achieved by providing a model graph integrated with a data graph for social, economic, health and environmental impact assessment of chemicals and materials.

Through its research and innovation (R&I) approaches, INSIGHT aims to foster a paradigm shift in the assessment of sustainability and safety of chemicals and materials, from the current fragmented situation towards a holistic and integrated approach. INSIGHT will use the SSbD principles and Life Cycle thinking approach to consider the intrinsic properties of chemicals and materials, production phase, end-user utilisation phase, and functionalities of the product for a comprehensive social, economic, health and environmental impact assessment.

Health impacts will be assessed through hazard and risk models, while environmental impacts will be assessed through Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), following the Product Environmental Footprint methodology. Socio-economic impacts will also be addressed using the [social-LCA framework](#)³ and Life Cycle Costing principles. INSIGHT will integrate all the above-mentioned approaches into a unified platform and to provide a user-friendly, FAIR and integrated framework for data-driven artificial intelligence (AI) methods that democratise AI for health and impact assessment and decision-making.

1.2 Re-confirmation and updating of the INSIGHT R&I Strategy

The aim of Task 1.1 is the collaborative re-confirmation and fine-tuning of the INSIGHT research and innovation (R&I) strategy in the first six months of the project. As presented in the current deliverable report, this re-confirmation and fine-tuning has included:

- (a) The detailed planning of timelines and data collection logistics considering their integration into the INSIGHT integrated SSbD analysis (WP4). The arrangement of data flows and the definition of data reporting practices has been mapped out (to support tasks T1.4 and T4.4).
- (b) Reconfirmation of stakeholder engagement approaches was achieved through a value proposition workshop with all INSIGHT partners. The agreed-upon communication channels have been passed over to WPs 5 and 6 for implementation.
- (c) Refinement and detailed planning for the INSIGHT Case Studies (CS), with industry and academic leads confirmed, the core research hypotheses and questions established, the datasets and models that are currently available inventoried and determination of the models that need to be developed within INSIGHT. A set of key performance indicators (KPIs) for evaluation of the INSIGHT CSs have also been elaborated.

During the kick-off meeting and in the subsequent WPI and joint WPI-WP2-WP3 meetings, the details of the available datasets were discussed and collated, and an inventory of the models that could be

³ <https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/iata/>

applied to the individual case studies was compiled. The overall strategy and focus on specific areas, including 2D materials, PFAS, Synthetic Amorphous Silica (SAS) and antimicrobial materials was confirmed, and the details of the case studies, and the key questions they would address, and the key modelling integration innovations they would demonstrate were documented during weekly meetings in February, March, April and May 2024.

2 The INSIGHT integrated SSbD framework

2.1 Mapping of the existing data landscape

2.1.1 Data landscape for social LCA

The data landscape for social LCA comprises several commercial and open databases, which provide typically country- and industry-level data on the average social impacts of production activities in different sectors. These include [Soca](#)⁴, [PSILCA](#)⁵, and [SHDB](#)⁶ that are specific to social LCA methodology, several industry- and company-level databases developed to support social sustainability assessment in companies (e.g., [Datamaran](#)⁷, [Ecovadis](#)⁸, [RepRisk](#)⁹ and [Sedex](#)¹⁰), as well as statistics and databases provided by NGOs (e.g., ILO, UN, OECD, and World Bank). However, as recognized in several studies and reports, the data landscape for social LCA has several challenges, including the resource-intensive nature of site-specific data collection (Moltesen et al., 2018), coarse level of aggregation and gaps in database data (Sureau et al., 2018; Viadurre et al., 2022), and data limitations for determining ‘absolute’ performance reference points for socio-economic impact indicators that include quantitative, semi-quantitative, and qualitative indicators (e.g., Carmo et al., 2017; Siebert et al., 2018).

The two main data sources utilised for social LCA in INSIGHT are (i) site-specific data from companies that support the case studies, and (ii) data from social LCA databases (Soca / PSILCA). These are complemented with public sources (e.g., reports, statistics and open databases provided by NGOs) highlighted in previous reports (e.g., Harmens & Gedkoop, 2021; [PSIA Handbook](#)¹¹; [UNEP, 2020](#)¹²). To specify data needs, we have analysed the indicators used in existing social LCA frameworks and empirical studies focused on materials and chemicals comparable to INSIGHT case studies. On this

⁴ <https://nexus.openlca.org/database/soca>; SOCA is an add-on for the ecoinvent LCI databases providing information for Social LCA, developed by [GreenDelta](#). It contains more than 70 social indicators addressing different sub-categories of four stakeholder groups for all activities/processes in the ecoinvent LCI databases.

⁵ <https://psilca.net/>; PSILCA (the Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment database) from GreenDelta allows calculation of social impacts of products along the entire life cycles, and detection of social hotspots.

⁶ <http://www.socialhotspot.org/>; SHDB (The Social Hotspots Database) provides solutions for continuous improvements for companies who aim to have a socially responsible supply chain. SHDB empowers buyers and suppliers by giving them the tools to assess sector-specific risks and opportunities.

⁷ <https://www.datamaran.com/>, an AI platform to help business leaders navigate the complex ESG landscape.

⁸ <https://ecovadis.com/>, a platform to help manage ESG risk and compliance, meet corporate sustainability goals, and drive impact at scale by guiding sustainability performance improvement of companies / value chains.

⁹ <https://www.reprisk.com/>, the largest database on ESG risks with 17+ years of unbroken data history.

¹⁰ <https://www.sedex.com/>, a tool for sustainable supply chains, underpinned by an extensive database.

¹¹ [PSIA Handbook](#)

¹² UNEP, 2020: <https://www.unep.org/resources/report/guidelines-social-life-cycle-assessment-products>

basis, we have formed a preliminary hierarchy of impact categories and indicators (see Appendix I), which is used as a basis for collecting site-specific data on the case studies.

2.1.2 Data landscape for Transcriptomics

Transcriptomic data will be extracted from public databases such as Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO¹³) and ArrayExpress¹⁴. The selection of datasets will be based on several criteria as described in Saarimäki et al. 2021. Datasets will be excluded if they have less than three replications, have unclear methodologies, have unavailable or missing data, or lack controls for each experimental group.

2.2 Mapping of the existing modelling landscape

The INSIGHT modelling landscape will encompass a diverse array of methodologies and tools designed to predict and assess chemical impacts. These models will be integrated in the form of a model graph, where the individual tools/models/functionalities will represent the nodes of the graph, and edges between models will be added based on their I/O compatibility. This will be the substrate for the definition of computational pipelines that will support the different case studies.

A vast collection of QSAR and PBK models will be provided through the [Jaqpot modelling platform](#)¹⁵. The Jaqpot platform is an advanced computational tool designed for in silico modelling and predictive analytics, particularly in the fields of chemical and material safety assessment. Jaqpot supports the development, validation, and deployment of predictive models for toxicological assessment and other related applications. It allows for the use of various machine learning algorithms. The platform provides both a graphical user interface (GUI) and a RESTful API, facilitating ease of use for both novice and experienced users. This dual access enables integration with other systems and supports a wide range of applications, from simple data analysis to complex predictive modelling. Jaqpot includes capabilities to handle data from electronic images and other sources, ensuring comprehensive analysis and model building. The platform is designed to be cloud-ready, supporting scalable and efficient model deployment and management. This makes it suitable for large-scale applications and collaborative projects involving multiple stakeholders.

In addition, advanced tools for toxicogenomic data modelling will be employed to elucidate the mechanisms of action of chemicals. The INSIGHT tools for omics data analysis will include state-of-the-art methodologies for omics data preprocessing (eUTOPIA, as described in Marwah et al., 2019), tools for transcriptomic-based benchmark dose analysis (BMDx, as described in Serra et al., 2020) and a tool for adverse outcome pathways (AOP) enrichment to give mechanistic interpretation of the effects of chemical exposure (AOP fingerprint, as described in Saarimäki et al., 2022). By analysing omics data, these tools provide insights into how chemicals interact with biological systems at a molecular level, revealing potential adverse effects and pathways of toxicity.

The model collection will also include the [INTEGRA tool](#) for environmental fate, exposure, and internal dose assessments. Computational methodologies for LCA and SLCA will also be implemented.

¹³ Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO): <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>

¹⁴ ArrayExpress: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress>

¹⁵ Jaqpot: <https://app.jaqpot.org>

The model landscape for social LCA remains underdeveloped. To our current knowledge, there are no directly applicable quantified impact pathway models that would comprehensively cover the different socio-economic impact categories. Developments will be continually monitored and the applicability of available impact pathway models, specifically for health and safety-related indicators (e.g., Sureau et al., 2020), will be investigated. More broadly, the model landscape for social LCA consists of existing methodological frameworks. The three most relevant, which are used as a basis in INSIGHT, are [UNEP \(2020\)](#)¹⁶ Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations (providing most comprehensive overview of the social LCA methodology), [PSIA \(2020\)](#) Product Social Impact Assessment Handbook¹⁷ (with focus on applicability of social LCA methodology in business contexts), and the World Business Council for Sustainable Development ([WBCSD, 2016](#))¹⁸ Social Life Cycle Metrics for Chemical Products (with focus on the assessment of the social impact of chemical products). In addition, models developed in academic research to support SSbD assessment for materials and chemicals are consulted (e.g., Pucciarelli et al., 2021; Stoycheva et al., 2022; Subramanian et al., 2018) as basis for model development.

2.3 Mapping of the workflows and dependencies

To leverage omics data in the different case studies, robust pipelines must be established for seamless processing and analysis. This will be done following the approach laid out in our previous efforts, including the NextCast software suite (Serra et al., 2022).

These workflows transform raw omics data into insights for safety and risk assessments. The pipeline begins with the eUTOPIA tool (Marwah et al., 2019, which preprocesses and normalises omics data, yielding gene expression data and a list of deregulated molecules, including differentially expressed genes. The normalised data from eUTOPIA is then processed by the BMDx tool (Serra et al., 2020) to identify dose-dependent genes and calculate their effective doses (Benchmark Dose, benchmark dose (lower confidence limit) - BMDL, benchmark dose (upper confidence limit) - BMDU). This is crucial for understanding dose-response relationships and identifying genes responsive to chemical exposure. Finally, the list of dose-dependent genes from BMDx is analysed by the AOP fingerprint tool (Saarimäki et al., 2022). This tool identifies potential molecular initiating events, key events, and adverse outcomes linked to chemical exposure, providing insights into the mechanisms of action and potential health risks. The workflow is shown schematically in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Possible pipeline for omics data analysis in the INSIGHT framework.

¹⁶ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Guidelines-for-Social-Life-Cycle-Assessment-of-Products-and-Organizations-2020-22.1.21sml.pdf>

¹⁷ <https://ciraig.org/index.php/project/product-social-impact-assessment-handbook/>

¹⁸ <https://www.wbcasd.org/Projects/Chemicals/Resources/Social-Life-Cycle-Metrics-for-Chemical-Products>

2.4 INSIGHT Data Reporting and quality Assessment

Reporting and quality assessment are crucial components of any model development process, as they ensure transparent communication, accountability, and the overall reliability of the models being developed, all of which are necessary components in informed decision-making. In today's data-driven world, where models are increasingly used to inform critical decisions across various domains, it is imperative to establish clear standards and protocols for reporting and evaluating model performance and applicability. Transparent and well-structured reporting not only facilitates the understanding and interpretation of models, but also enables reproducibility, validation, and quality assessment.

The INSIGHT model-reporting framework will adopt three distinct templates: the QSAR Model Reporting Format (QMRF), the MODA template and the physiologically-based kinetic (PBK) reporting template introduced by the recent [OECD guidelines](#)¹⁹.

The scientific community of QSAR modelling has adopted the QMRF format for promoting transparency and reproducibility. The QMRF standardised template was jointly developed by the JRC and EU Member State authorities to condense and document crucial details of QSAR models and their corresponding validation findings. It adheres to the OECD validation principles, encompassing a specified endpoint (the predicted outcome), a clear algorithm (a reproducible method for generating predictions), a defined scope of applicability (indicating the model's relevance to specific predictions), comprehensive assessments of goodness-of-fit, robustness, and predictivity (evaluating the model's effectiveness), and, when feasible, a mechanistic interpretation (clarifying how numerical outcomes relate to biological changes). An updated version of the [QMRF reporting template](#)²⁰ has been released recently.

The European Materials Modelling Council (EMMC) developed the Materials Modelling Data (MODA) reporting template to report the details of physics-based modelling approaches, based on the [Review of Materials Modelling \(RoMM\)](#). MODA's objective is to systematically describe and document simulations and models, detailing the user case, methods for solving, and post-processing techniques employed. The template guides modellers and users towards comprehensive, high-level documentation of materials models, beginning with end-user cases and incorporating all relevant computational details necessary for model reproducibility, curation, and interfacing with other models. Although initially designed for physics-based materials models, the MODA template can also be applied to data-driven and machine learning models, such as QSAR approaches, utilising the same framework and structure. Recently, similar concepts have emerged for describing workflows for data-centric models employed across various applications (Combemale et al., 2021). Within INSIGHT, work has been underway, in collaboration with the Horizon Europe project [WorldFAIR](#), to demonstrate a systematic and harmonised approach to complete MODA templates, thus reducing error, formulated via a web application called EasyMODA. Figure 3 shows a schematic of each step taken in the Easy-MODA platform to generalise model data generalisation, which is central to our test case scenario. The left panel of Figure 3 shows the Easy-MODA GUI, where users initiate the modelling process. Here, detailed project information is inputted, including project title, acronym, description, and details of the models to be used—whether physics-based, relying on fundamental principles, or data-based, utilising empirical datasets. The demonstration case consists of both a physics-based model and a data-based model. As a final outcome from the combination of these models, the adverse effect class (non-toxic

¹⁹ <https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/guidance-document-on-the-characterisation-validation-and-reporting-of-physiologically-based-kinetic-models-for-regulatory-purposes.pdf>

²⁰ [https://one.oecd.org/document/ENV/CBC/MONO\(2023\)32/ANN1/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/ENV/CBC/MONO(2023)32/ANN1/en/pdf)

or toxic) of Ag, TiO₂, and CuO nanoparticles to the HepaRG cell lines is predicted based on their properties at atomic level (Varsou et al., 2024).

Figure 3. The Easy-MODA Interface Workflow from Input to Output Documentation. The image captures the step-by-step process of using the Easy-MODA system, starting from data entry in the GUI, through the editing modules for physics-based and data-based models, to the final output of a harmonised MODA document. This output encapsulates the project overview and simulation details, showcasing the system's efficacy in automating and documenting materials modelling workflows represented here by a nanoparticle toxicity simulation.

PBK models are mechanistic models for predicting species-specific internal concentration profiles after chemical exposure and are increasingly used in next-generation risk assessment frameworks. As such, comprehensive documentation is essential for regulatory acceptance and use in risk assessment pipelines. The OECD's PBK model reporting guidelines offers a comprehensive framework that ensures thorough documentation, facilitating model validation and regulatory acceptance. These guidelines aim to enhance regulatory acceptance without relying on *in vivo* data, addressing both model developers and risk assessors. They instruct model developers on proper model development and documentation, while offering a checklist for risk assessors to review the models. The template begins with metadata, followed by a summary of key modelling aspects such as development, characterization, validation, and regulatory applicability. It includes a detailed characterization section with steps for problem formulation, model conceptualization, parameterization, implementation, performance, and documentation. Subsequent sections address uncertainties, specify software used, list peer reviews, comprehensively record parameter values and sources, and conclude with a references section.

2.4.1 Social LCA

Due to the aforementioned limitations with social LCA data quality, transparent data quality assessment will be performed as part of case study investigation. While there is no comprehensive guidance for data quality management in social LCA, some general tools are presented (e.g., PSIA, 2020; UNEP, 2020). In INSIGHT, we will utilize the pedigree matrix for data quality assessment (Eisfeld & Citroth, 2017; Orola et al., 2022; UNEP, 2020). The matrix consists of five indicators, addressing (i) the

reliability of the sources, and the conformance of the data in terms of (ii) completeness, (iii) time, (iv) geography, and (v) technology (Eisfeldt & Ciroth, 2017). For each of the five areas of quality assessment, a score from 1 (very good) to 5 (very bad) is assigned, providing a quantitative assessment of data quality associated with each socio-economic indicator used.

The type of data used for socio-economic impacts will be reported along with the reference scale model used. However, case-specific data will be treated as confidential and cannot be publicly reported.

3 Initial INSIGHT Stakeholder Engagement

3.1 Clustering of projects (HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-21-22-23)

Clustering of projects funded under specific and related topics is an important aspect of driving synergies, and for INSIGHT clustering with the sister projects provides opportunities for data sharing to increase the knowledge graph, and for testing and refining models developed in INSIGHT for use with other datasets.

A first clustering activity, organised by the [PINK](#) project, took place virtually on 21st March 2024, whereby the coordinators and partners of the sister projects met and exchanged ideas. The aim of this meeting was to identify common topics and interests between the project and to possibly coordinate common dissemination activities to regulatory or standardisation agencies.

A face to face Resilience-2023 Networking meeting is planned to take place on Monday, 17 June, 14:00-19:00 as part of the [MaterialsWeek 2024](#) conference. In addition to a poster session where each project presents its planned work there are also three speakers, representing [AMI2030](#), [IRISS](#) and [PARC](#) as key initiatives with which the resilience projects will interact.. A round table discussion of how to collaborate and key topics for cross-project working groups will be implemented.

3.2 Engagement with PARC via SynNet

PARC, the Partnership for Assessment of the Risks of Chemicals, has established [SYNnet](#), a network designed to facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing with other initiatives focusing on environmental, food, and human health issues and organizations working in the field of chemical risk assessment. The aim of SYNnet is to advance research and innovation in chemical risk assessment through establishing official synergies.

A SYNnet “application to collaborate with INSIGHT” was submitted by PARC WP7 (UoB Co-Lead) and an the application has been circulated to PARC WP Leads to consider where there are synergies and opportunities for collaboration and joint work. Clear areas of collaboration exist in terms of transcriptomics data management, development and validation of adverse outcome pathways (AOP) and their FAIRification, the the integration of INSIGHT’s tools into the PARC Safe and Sustainable by Design toolbox. As this discussion progresses it will be mapped into the Stakeholder Roadmap to ensure that the relationships are managed and maintained effectively.

4 The INSIGHT Case Studies

4.1 Overview of the INSIGHT Case Studies – goals and objectives

INSIGHT will develop an integrated computational framework for evaluating the impact of chemicals and materials, benefiting academic researchers, regulatory authorities, industrial stakeholders, and NGOs, and demonstrate the utility of the integrated in silico framework via the case studies, each of which targets (1) a different class of chemicals or materials; (2) a different industrial application area (batteries and electronics, fire fighting chemicals, antimicrobial coatings and bio-based tyre materials); (3) a different set of models and tools that will be integrated through alignment of the data inputs and outputs and the integration of the models through user-friendly workflows to address the needs of the specific case study; (4) a different aspect of the regulatory landscape such as demonstrating an improved safety profile for REACH, or demonstrating increased sustainability and reduced water or carbon footprints of a product or synthesis route; and (5) a different scientific or regulatory question that can be answered only through the innovative integration of currently disparate modelling approaches. *Thus, the success of the INSIGHT case studies will be their demonstration of the innovative integration of models and the new technical and societal insights that can be gained through this integration.*

Integration of socio-economic impacts of the case studies will be used to test and further develop INSIGHT'S approach to social LCA in alignment with the principles of SSbD (Caldeira et al., 2022a, b). Through the case studies, more comprehensive understanding of the socio-economic benefits and risks of the case study chemicals and materials will be developed. In addition, the diversity of the case studies, as described below, supports the development of INSIGHT'S social LCA approach toward applicability to different types of materials and at different levels of technological readiness.

The INSIGHT Case studies will be presented through an intuitive graphical user interface (GUI) and will include the development of decision maps to guide users from diverse backgrounds, enhancing their ability to participate in decision-making processes. Academic researchers can study the impact of chemicals and materials on human health and the environment; regulatory authorities can provide more robust guidelines for safe chemical use and disposal; industrial stakeholders can evaluate the impact of different materials and chemicals on their operations and supply chains; NGOs can identify chemicals/materials that pose risks to vulnerable populations or ecosystems.

Figure 4 shows a summary of the Case studies, with further details of each provided below, including a summary of the available data, the models that will be applied and the key questions to be addressed. These are initial ideas, as of June 2024, and that the Case studies will evolve as they progress and as new ideas and opportunities arise. We will ensure cross-pollination of the case studies, through sharing of approaches and solutions identified, to enable the cases to progress synergistically. While 4 case studies are outlined below, INSIGHT'S DoA commits to delivery of 2 completed case studies, so decisions will be made along the way as to which case studies to use for the demonstration of the INSIGHT computational framework overall.

| Antimicrobial materials |
|--|---|--|--|
| Leads:
Beatriz Alonso - Graphenea
Peter Wick - EMPA | Leads:
Third party (via UPO)
Francesco Dondero- UPO | Leads:
Guilherme Brunetto - Solvay
Iseult Lynch - UoB | Leads:
Gottlieb Linder - Evonik
Peter Wick - EMPA |
| Key questions for CS:
What is the impact of graphene in composites on durability? recyclability? On | Key questions for CS:
To show the feasibility of replacing PFAS containing technical materials (adhesives, coatings, fluids, greases and lubricants) in strategic industrial sectors, e.g. avionics | Key questions for CS:
To replace the existing chemically-derived materials with bio-based raw materials | Key questions for CS:
NMs versus regular disinfectants
Bound versus unbound actives
Leaching / degradation rates |
| Modelling approaches needed:
-Toxicity - QSAR
- Recyclability modeling (see e.g., Reuter & van Schaik)
- Model policy scenarios
Integrate LCA & KnowledgeGraph | Modelling approaches needed:
-Toxicity -QSAR
-Exposure / intake
-Omics and AOP
Integrate functional analysis / multi-criteria optimisation models | Modelling approaches needed:
- materials modelling (for functionality, SSbD)
- LCA comparing the 2 production routes (chem vs bio)
Integrate materials models &LCA | Modelling approaches needed:
- Fate modelling (degradation)
- LCA and recyclability
- Toxicity - QSAR
- integrated safe & sustainability / overall IATA |

Figure 4. High level summary of the INSIGHT Case studies, based on the intensive process of discussion and refinement carried out during the first 5 months of the project, and the data and model collection activities of WPs 2 and 3 to understand what is available currently and what development is needed to deliver the case studies.

4.2 Case Study summaries

4.2.1 Advanced materials including 2D materials - Graphene

Among the different materials that are currently being developed and used in various commercial applications, INSIGHT will focus on Graphene as an exemplar 2D material and consider its application for construction/composites and energy applications. Graphene has unique properties that make it a promising candidate for energy-related and construction material applications, such as energy storage, conversion, and harvesting, and improved structural properties enabling the use of less concrete. Graphene has a high surface area, excellent electrical conductivity, and good mechanical properties, making it a potential candidate for energy storage applications like batteries and supercapacitors, and as an additive in construction/polymer materials. Graphene and other 2D materials have been studied for energy harvesting applications, such as piezoelectric and thermoelectric generators.

Although it is difficult to estimate the market size for graphene due to the diverse range of potential applications, the global graphene market size was valued at EUR 221.9 million in 2020 and is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 38.7% from 2021 to 2028. From a socio-economic perspective, graphene thus shows significant potential for economic value creation due to rapid forecasted market growth, high value of the material, and innovation potential in many application areas (e.g., da Costa & Hussain, 2020). At the same time, many uncertainties remain on the impact of graphene, especially when integrated in consumer products and used globally. For example, research associates graphene nanoparticles with potential health, safety, and environmental risks that can affect workers in the production stage as well as users of graphene-containing products (e.g., Arvidsson et al., 2013; Osmond & McCall, 2010; Spinazze et al., 2016; O'Brien & Cummins, 2008).

The INSIGHT framework will make use of an unprecedented amount of curated and integrated data to guide the mechanistic evaluation of the impact of AdMa, using Graphene for construction and energy applications as a benchmark for 2D materials.

4.2.1.1 The Graphene materials and the Graphene case study objectives

The focus of this section is to outline the objectives and key components of the graphene, particularly Graphene-oxide (GO) case study, particularly emphasizing toxicology, sustainability, and socio-economic assessments. This involves evaluating the environmental impact of GO throughout its lifecycle, from cradle to grave, ensuring that all aspects of its use are considered.

Table I provides a comprehensive overview of the various challenges associated with the production and application of graphene oxide (GO), highlighting environmental, health, economic, performance, sustainability, and regulatory issues.

Recent literature highlights several important clues into the environmental and health impacts of GO. Research indicates that GO can cause oxidative stress in exposed human cells and aquatic organisms, emphasizing the need for careful environmental impact assessments. In literature, there is a substantial amount of data on the toxicological and ecotoxicological properties of GO. This data is crucial for establishing Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationships (QSARs), which predict potential risks based on chemical structures, facilitating safer and more informed development of new materials. In addition, studies show that the biodegradability of GO can be enhanced through chemical functionalization, a critical factor for developing environmentally sustainable applications.

Table 1: Summary of challenges associated with conventional GO, which forms the basis of this case study.

Issue	Description
Environmental Impact	High energy consumption, resource depletion, and pollution from chemical use during production.
Health and Safety	Risks to workers from exposure to graphene dust, potential respiratory issues, and safety concerns during production and disposal. Difficulties to predict graphene oxide toxicity.
Economic Issues	High production costs due to energy-intensive processes and supply chain vulnerabilities related to raw material availability and price fluctuations. Difficult acceptability of nanomaterials in the market due to concerns over safety and regulatory hurdles.
Sustainability	Difficulties in recycling and managing end-of-life products containing graphene oxide, hindering the development of a circular economy.
Regulatory Compliance	Difficulties to regulate Graphene-oxide based materials due to their heterogeneity and the industry's challenges in accepting the application of the precautionary principle.

Efforts are being made to develop greener synthesis methods for GO, such as using electrochemical processes that reduce the use of harsh chemicals and improve the material's environmental footprint. These advancements are crucial for mitigating the environmental impacts associated with the production and use of GO. A foundational basis for the sustainability assessment of GO is provided by Beloin-Saint-Pierre and Hischier (2021). Hischier's research includes life cycle assessments (LCA) and evaluations of the environmental impacts of GO from production to disposal. This work serves as a critical starting point for assessing the overall sustainability of GO applications.

For the socio-economic assessment, additional discussions might be necessary regarding the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of GO applications. Evaluating the maturity of the technology and its market readiness is essential for supporting a comprehensive socio-economic assessment. This helps in understanding the potential economic impact and viability of GO in various industries.

In INSIGHT, the leadership of the GO case study is guaranteed by INSIGHT's partner Graphenea, a leading manufacturer of GO in Europe and an Insight partner. Graphenea's GO has been featured in several dozen scientific papers, providing a wealth of toxicity data, LCA assessments, and physical-chemical characterizations. This extensive dataset will be invaluable in conducting comprehensive analyses and ensuring the robustness of the INSIGHT's findings.

Additionally, we will benchmark Graphenea's GO against other materials using literature data gathered and assessed from the Graphene Flagship project. INSIGHT's partner EMPA's involvement in this EU initiative facilitates access to a broad range of comparative data, ensuring that our assessments are thorough and reflective of the latest advancements in the field.

In summary, the GO case study aims to leverage the extensive data on the material's toxicological and ecological effects, build on established sustainability frameworks, and enhance socio-economic assessments by evaluating technology maturity

4.2.1.2 Regulatory Landscape for the Graphene case study

The regulatory environment for graphene oxide-based batteries in the European Union (EU) encompasses several key frameworks and regulations addressing chemical safety, product safety, and environmental sustainability. A snapshot of the regulatory landscape is presented below:

1. REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals) Regulation:
 - Chemical Registration: Graphene oxide is registered under REACH as it is produced or imported in quantities of one tonne or more per year (see [REACH dossier here](#)²¹).
 - Safety Assessment: Manufacturers and importers must provide safety data and risk assessments for graphene oxide to ensure it does not pose a risk to human health or the environment.
2. a) Battery Directive (Directive 2006/66/EC):
 - Collection and Recycling: Sets requirements for the collection, treatment, recycling, and disposal of batteries. Manufacturers must ensure proper waste management and recycling processes for graphene oxide-based batteries.
 - Labelling: Batteries must be properly labelled to inform consumers about their chemical composition and safe disposal methods.
- b) Structural codes of concrete
 - Defined by each country.
3. Restriction of Hazardous Substances (RoHS) Directive:
 - Substance Restrictions: Regulates the use of specific hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment. While graphene oxide itself may not be restricted, other materials in the battery may be subject to these rules.
4. Ecodesign Directive (Directive 2009/125/EC):
 - Energy Efficiency: Sets requirements for the energy efficiency and environmental impact of energy-related products, including batteries. This may influence the design and lifecycle management of graphene oxide-based batteries.
5. Waste Framework Directive (Directive 2008/98/EC):
 - Waste Management: Establishes a legal framework for treating and managing waste in the EU. Producers of graphene oxide-based batteries must adhere to waste hierarchy principles: prevention, reuse, recycling, and disposal.
6. CLP (Classification, Labelling, and Packaging) Regulation:
 - Hazard Communication: Requires proper classification, labelling, and packaging of chemical substances, including graphene oxide. This ensures that hazards are clearly communicated to users.
7. Safety and Performance Standards:
 - Compliance: Batteries must meet various safety and performance standards, which may be specified by European standards bodies such as CENELEC (European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization).
8. Environmental and Health Assessments:
 - Lifecycle Impact: Manufacturers may need to conduct lifecycle assessments to evaluate the environmental and health impacts of graphene oxide-based batteries from production to disposal.

²¹ REACH dossier for GO (EC number 947-768-1): <https://chem.echa.europa.eu/100.260.251/dossier-list/reach/dossiers/active?searchText=Reaction%20product%20of%20Graphite.%20acid-trea>

4.2.1.3 Initial results from sLCA on the GO case study

INSIGHT's approach to social LCA has been piloted with the GO case study. Based on inventory data made available by Graphenea, the production system was modelled for a cradle-to-gate analysis comparing conventional concrete with GO-infused concrete assuming an improved lifetime with GO. The results display the social risk levels of analyzed scenarios on 50 distinct social and socio-economic indicators (organized into 4 stakeholder categories and 17 sub-categories), revealing some differences that are sensitive to assumptions regarding the impact of GO on concrete lifetime. In addition, a preliminary life cycle costing analysis was performed to assess the economic feasibility of Graphene oxide production. Due to confidentiality, these results – based on financial data from Graphenea – cannot be disclosed but they serve as basis for developing the approach for economic impact assessment.

Figure 5: Results of social LCA at impact sub-category level, comparing GO-infused concrete with conventional concrete of equivalent strength in two lifetime extension scenarios (+30%, +50%). Unit (risk hours) calculated as the risk level (of contributing production processes) x activity variable (working hours of contributing production processes, reflecting human contribution).

In general, the social LCA results enable the comparison of social risks between multiple scenarios, supporting the selection of best options from socio-economic perspectives. The social LCA results also support the identification of largest potential social risk areas in GO production, which can guide more detailed analysis, planning of interventions, and monitoring actions by Graphenea. Identified challenges include, first, the limitations of the social LCA method, which quantifies social risks using reference scales. For this reason, the indicator values are not direct measures of social effects caused

by the focal product system, but instead offer a way to identify highest social risk areas on relative terms. This calls for further work to allow the integration of social LCA the causal AOP model of INSIGHT. Second, social LCA results are affected by assumptions in the inventory building stage as well as the quality of social indicator data across the production system. Thus, continuing attention to inventory specification and utilization of context-specific data is required to ensure sufficient quality of results whilst ensuring that social LCA remains viable to execute as part of the integrated AOP model.

4.2.2 Advanced materials - Synthetic Amorphous Silica (SAS)

INSIGHT will utilise synthetic amorphous silica (SAS) nanoparticles for automotive applications, as the other exemplar advanced material. This case study focuses on the environmental and socio-economic impacts of newer green synthesis methods to ensure that these are actually better for the environment and society than the traditional routes of generation of SAS by grinding of sand.

The addition of amorphous silica to the tyre compound helps to improve the mechanical properties of the tyre and thus increase its performance, such as increased grip (due to the increased surface area in contact with the asphalt, increasing the safety of tyres), reduced rolling resistance (in turn reducing the fuel consumption and lowering CO₂ emissions) or increased durability (leading to longer tread life and reduced waste).

The market size of amorphous silica in the tire market is substantial and has been growing in recent years due to the increasing demand for high-performance tyres with better safety and environmental performance. The global amorphous silica market size was valued at EUR 2.7 billion in 2020 and is projected to reach EUR 4.4 billion by 2025, at a CAGR of 10.3% during the forecast period²², reflecting the material's potential to contribute to economic growth. Although the economic potential and improvement to driving safety mentioned above point to clear benefits, there are few more comprehensive analyses on the socio-economic risks and benefits associated with amorphous silica (although Purker et al. (2023) indicate a relatively neutral socio-economic performance vis-a-vis commonly used referents).

4.2.2.1 The challenges with SAS in tyres and the basis for the case study

Synthetic Amorphous Silica (SAS) is commonly used in the production of tyres due to its ability to enhance various performance characteristics such as wet grip, fuel efficiency, and tread durability. However, the conventional production and use of SAS in tyres come with several problems and challenges. Among the issues with conventional SAS (summarised in Table 2) are:

A. Environmental Impact

- **Resource Depletion / Raw Materials:** Conventional SAS is typically derived from non-renewable sources such as quartz sand. The extraction and processing of these materials contribute to resource depletion.
- **Energy Consumption due to high energy production process:** The production of conventional SAS, particularly through methods such as the fumed (pyrogenic) process, requires significant energy input, leading to high carbon emissions.

²² <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/4807888/colloidal-silica-silica-sol-a-global-market>

- **Pollution arising from chemical use:** The production process involves the use of strong acids and bases, which can result in chemical waste and pollution if not managed properly.

B. Health and Safety Concerns

- **Exposure Risks and Worker Safety:** Manufacturing and handling SAS can expose workers to silica dust, which poses respiratory risks. Prolonged inhalation of fine silica particles can lead to conditions such as silicosis.
- **Product Safety and End-User Risks:** While embedded in the tyre matrix, there is minimal risk to end-users. However, during production and disposal, there can be concerns regarding exposure to airborne particles.

C. Economic and Supply Chain Issues

- **High Production Costs:** The energy-intensive nature of conventional SAS production can lead to high manufacturing costs, which can be passed on to consumers.
- **Supply Chain Vulnerability due to raw material supply limitations:** Dependence on specific raw materials can create vulnerabilities in the supply chain, especially with fluctuating availability and prices of quartz sand.

D. Performance Trade-offs

Balancing properties of functional performance and safety /sustainability: While SAS improves wet grip and fuel efficiency, achieving an optimal balance between different performance characteristics (e.g., wet grip vs. rolling resistance) can be challenging. Additionally, balancing performance and sustainability can be difficult when considering alternatives

E. Sustainability and Circular Economy

End-of-Life Management: Conventional SAS in tyres presents challenges for recycling and disposal. Current tyre recycling processes are not fully equipped to recover or repurpose SAS efficiently.

F. Regulatory Compliance

Compliance Costs: Meeting stringent environmental and health regulations can add to the cost and complexity of using conventional SAS in tyre production. Compliance with regulations such as REACH and the Industrial Emissions Directive requires significant investment in safety measures and pollution control technologies.

Table 2: Summary of the challenges associated with conventional SAS for tyres, which forms the basis of the SAS case study.

Issue	Description
Environmental Impact	High energy consumption, resource depletion, and pollution from chemical use during production.
Health and Safety	Risks to workers from exposure to silica dust, potential respiratory issues, and safety concerns during production and disposal.
Economic Issues	High production costs due to energy-intensive processes and supply chain vulnerabilities related to raw material availability and price fluctuations.

Performance / Safety Trade-offs Challenges in balancing wet grip, fuel efficiency, and rolling resistance to optimise tyre performance whilst also maximising sustainability and safety.

Sustainability Difficulties in recycling and managing end-of-life tyres containing conventional SAS, hindering the development of a circular economy.

Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach, including the development and adoption of bio-based SAS, improvements in production technologies, and enhanced recycling methods, and application of advanced informatics approaches.

4.2.2.2 SAS materials and the different synthesis routes (conventional and from renewable resources)

The synthesis of SAS can follow conventional or bio-based routes. Each method has distinct characteristics, processes, and implications for sustainability, as summarised in Table 3. Below is a comparison of the two routes:

A. Conventional Synthesis of Synthetic Amorphous Silica

1. Raw Materials:

- Silica Sand: The primary source of silicon dioxide (SiO_2), extracted from natural deposits.
- Chemicals: Sodium silicate (water glass) and other chemicals used in precipitation processes.

2. Processes:

- Precipitation Method:
 - Alkaline Extraction: Silica sand is dissolved in sodium hydroxide to form sodium silicate.
 - Acid Precipitation: Sodium silicate solution is neutralized with sulfuric acid, causing silica to precipitate.
 - Filtration and Washing: The precipitated silica is filtered, washed to remove impurities, and dried.
- Fumed (Pyrogenic) Method:
 - Vapor Phase Hydrolysis: Silicon tetrachloride (SiCl_4) is reacted with water vapor in a flame, producing fumed silica.
 - Collection: The resulting silica is collected as a fine, fluffy powder.

3. Characteristics:

- High Purity: Conventional methods yield high-purity silica.
- Controlled Particle Size: The precipitation method allows control over particle size and surface area.
- Energy Intensive: Especially the fumed method, which requires high temperatures.

4. Environmental Impact:

- High Energy Consumption: Significant energy required for extraction and processing.
- Chemical Use: Involves the use of strong acids and bases, with potential environmental risks.
- Resource Depletion: Relies on non-renewable silica sand deposits.

Bio-based Synthesis of Synthetic Amorphous Silica

1. Raw Materials:

- Biomass: Agricultural residues (e.g., rice husks, sugarcane bagasse), diatoms, or other silicon-accumulating plants.

- Waste Products: Industrial or agricultural by-products containing silica.

2. Processes:

- Extraction from Biomass:
 - Burning and Ashing: Biomass is burned to produce ash rich in silica.
 - Alkaline Extraction: Ash is treated with sodium hydroxide to dissolve silica, forming sodium silicate.
 - Acid Precipitation: Similar to conventional methods, the solution is neutralised to precipitate silica.
- Alternative Methods:
 - Bioleaching: Using microorganisms to extract silica from biomass.
 - Hydrothermal Processing: Treating biomass under high pressure and temperature to extract silica.

3. Characteristics:

- Renewable Resources: Utilises renewable and often waste materials.
- Lower Purity: May require additional purification steps to achieve the same purity levels as conventional silica.
- Energy Efficient: Generally, less energy-intensive compared to conventional methods.

4. Environmental Impact:

- Sustainable: Reduces reliance on non-renewable resources and utilises waste materials.
- Lower Carbon Footprint: Typically involves lower energy consumption and carbon emissions.
- Reduced Chemical Use: Some bio-based methods minimise the need for harsh chemicals.

Table 3: Summary of the comparison between conventional and bio-based synthesis of SAS

Aspect	Conventional Synthesis	Bio-based Synthesis
Raw Materials	Silica sand, sodium silicate, chemicals	Biomass, agricultural residues, waste products
Key Processes	Precipitation, fumed (pyrogenic)	Burning and ashing, bioleaching, hydrothermal
Purity	High	Lower, may require purification
Energy Consumption	High	Lower
Chemical Use	Significant (strong acids/bases)	Reduced
Environmental Impact	High energy, resource depletion, chemical risks	Sustainable, lower carbon footprint, less waste
Sustainability	Relies on non-renewable resources	Utilises renewable/waste materials
Cost	Potentially higher due to energy/chemical use	Potentially lower due to use of waste materials

While conventional methods of producing SAS are well-established and produce high-purity materials, bio-based methods offer a more sustainable and environmentally friendly alternative. The choice depends on factors like resource availability, required purity, and environmental considerations.

4.2.2.3 Regulatory Landscape for bio-based SAS materials

The regulatory landscape for bio-based SAS used in tyres in the European Union (EU) is multi-faceted, covering chemical safety, product safety, environmental impact, and specific industry standards. Below are the key regulatory frameworks and considerations:

A. REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals) Regulation (EC 1907/2006)

- **Registration:** Producers and importers of bio-based SAS in quantities of one tonne or more per year must register the substance with the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA). This includes providing comprehensive data on the properties, uses, and risks associated with SAS.
- **Evaluation:** ECHA evaluates the provided data to identify any potential risks to human health or the environment.
- **Authorisation and Restriction:** Specific uses of SAS may require authorisation, and any identified hazardous uses might be restricted.

B. CLP (Classification, Labelling, and Packaging) Regulation (EC 1272/2008)

- **Classification:** SAS must be classified based on its physical, health, and environmental hazards.
- **Labelling:** Proper labelling is required to indicate hazards, including pictograms, signal words, hazard statements, and precautionary statements.
- **Packaging:** SAS must be packaged in a manner that ensures safe handling and transport.

C. Tire Industry Regulations and Standards

- **EU Tire Labelling Regulation (EU Regulation 2020/740):** Tires must be labelled to provide information on fuel efficiency, wet grip, and noise levels. The use of SAS can impact these performance metrics and must be accurately reflected in the labelling.
- **European Tyre and Rim Technical Organisation (ETRTO) Standards:** Industry standards for the dimensions, load capacities, and performance of tyres that may indirectly affect the use of materials like SAS.

D. Environmental Legislation

- **Waste Framework Directive (Directive 2008/98/EC):** Regulates the management of waste, promoting recycling and proper disposal. This includes end-of-life tyres and the management of SAS as a component of tyre material.
- **Industrial Emissions Directive (Directive 2010/75/EU):** Controls emissions from industrial processes, including tyre manufacturing, to minimise environmental impacts.
- **REACH Annex XVII:** Includes restrictions on the use of certain substances in tyres to reduce environmental and health risks. Bio-based SAS must comply with these restrictions.

E. Sustainability and Circular Economy

- **Circular Economy Action Plan:** Encourages the use of sustainable materials, including bio-based components like SAS, in product design and manufacturing to promote resource efficiency and recycling.
- **Ecodesign Directive (Directive 2009/125/EC):** Promotes the development of products with improved environmental performance, which can influence the selection and use of materials like SAS in tyre manufacturing.

F. Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) Regulations

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- Workplace Exposure Limits: Employers must ensure that workers are not exposed to harmful levels of SAS dust during tyre production. Compliance with occupational exposure limits is required.
- Safety Data Sheets (SDS): Manufacturers must provide SDS for SAS, detailing safe handling practices and emergency measures.

G. Automotive Regulations

- EU General Safety Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2019/2144): Sets safety standards for vehicles, including tyres, ensuring they meet performance and safety requirements that could be influenced by the materials used.

4.2.3 Antimicrobial coating materials

The shortage of new antibiotics and antivirals, and an increase in multi-resistant organisms pose a significant risk to public health, as hardly learnt during the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the European Healthcare-associated Infections Surveillance Network ([HAI network](#)²³), around 3.2 million people suffer nosocomial infections in Europe every year, and about 37,000 people die as a direct consequence. (Nano-)metal oxide-based (silver, copper, etc) coatings and release systems, advanced oxidative surfaces generating radicals like TiO₂-based photocatalysis or metal-free systems were developed as novel alternatives to antibiotics. However, regulatory bodies and policy makers need to ensure the safety and conformity of these new solutions before authorisation. Since these materials and surfaces are considered as biocides, careful assessment is needed to avoid adverse societal and economic impacts as anticipated in the Green Deal of the European Commission. For example, it is important that the environmental and socio-economic risks associated with raw material extraction and production processes are identified and weighed against the benefits of reducing the number of infections (Pucciarelli et al., 2021). The market forecast for antimicrobial coating in the automotive, building, and textile sector is expected to increase the CARG between 3% and 9% by 2025.

INSIGHT will collect and structure existing data and inform SSbD, anticipating the use of nanometal and metal-free materials and surfaces as well as link the activities get started in Horizon Europe projects.

4.2.3.1 Antimicrobial materials and the case study objectives

The use of antimicrobial coatings, while beneficial in various applications, poses several safety and sustainability challenges. Here's a detailed analysis of the key problems associated with the safety and sustainability of antimicrobial coatings:

I. Human Health Concerns

Toxicity:

- **Acute and Chronic Effects:** Antimicrobial agents used in coatings, such as silver nanoparticles, triclosan, and quaternary ammonium compounds, can be toxic to humans if they leach out. Acute exposure can cause skin and respiratory irritation, while chronic exposure

²³ <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/about-us/partnerships-and-networks/disease-and-laboratory-networks/hai-net>

might lead to more severe health issues, including endocrine disruption and antibiotic resistance.

Allergic Reactions:

- **Sensitization:** Some antimicrobial agents can cause allergic reactions in sensitive individuals. Prolonged exposure, even at low levels, can lead to sensitization and allergic contact dermatitis.

Resistance Development:

- **Antibiotic Resistance:** Continuous use of antimicrobial coatings can contribute to the development of resistant strains of microorganisms. This is a significant public health concern as it can render standard treatments ineffective against resistant bacteria.

2. Environmental Impacts

Persistence and Bioaccumulation:

- **Environmental Persistence:** Many antimicrobial agents are persistent in the environment, meaning they do not break down easily and can accumulate in ecosystems.
- **Bioaccumulation:** Some antimicrobials, like heavy metal nanoparticles, can bioaccumulate in the food chain, affecting wildlife and potentially entering human food sources.

Ecotoxicity:

- **Harm to Non-target Organisms:** Antimicrobial agents can be toxic to aquatic and terrestrial organisms. For example, silver nanoparticles can be highly toxic to fish and other aquatic life.
- **Disruption of Microbial Ecosystems:** The widespread use of antimicrobial coatings can disrupt natural microbial communities, which play essential roles in environmental processes like nutrient cycling and waste decomposition.

3. Economic and Practical Issues

Cost:

- **High Production Costs:** The production of antimicrobial coatings can be expensive due to the cost of antimicrobial agents and the processes required to incorporate them effectively.
- **Maintenance and Reapplication:** Many antimicrobial coatings lose efficacy over time and require reapplication, adding to maintenance costs.

Efficacy and Durability:

- **Limited Longevity:** The antimicrobial efficacy of coatings can diminish over time, especially under conditions of wear and environmental exposure.
- **Variable Performance:** The effectiveness of antimicrobial coatings can vary significantly depending on the application, surface type, and environmental conditions.

4. Regulatory Challenges

Compliance:

- **Regulatory Approvals:** Antimicrobial coatings must comply with various regulations, such as the Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR) in Europe, which requires rigorous testing and approval processes. This can be time-consuming and costly.
- **Labelling and Safety Standards:** Products must meet strict labelling requirements and safety standards, ensuring users are informed about potential hazards and safe use practices.

5. Sustainability Concerns

Resource Use:

- **Non-renewable Resources:** Many antimicrobial agents are derived from non-renewable resources, contributing to resource depletion.
- **Sustainable Alternatives:** There is a need for the development of sustainable, bio-based antimicrobial agents that are effective and have a lower environmental impact.

End-of-Life Disposal:

- **Waste Management:** The disposal of materials treated with antimicrobial coatings can pose environmental risks if not managed properly. Ensuring that these products do not release harmful substances into the environment at the end of their life cycle is crucial.
- **Recycling Challenges:** The presence of antimicrobial agents can complicate the recycling of treated materials, limiting their reusability and contributing to waste.

Table 4. Summary of Problems with Safety and Sustainability of Antimicrobial Coatings

Issue	Description
Human Health Concerns	Toxicity, allergic reactions, and contribution to antibiotic resistance pose significant health risks.
Environmental Impact	Persistence, bioaccumulation, ecotoxicity, and disruption of microbial ecosystems.
Economic Issues	High production and maintenance costs, limited longevity, and variable performance.
Regulatory Challenges	Compliance with stringent regulations, labelling, and safety standards require significant effort and resources.
Sustainability Concerns	Dependence on non-renewable resources, end-of-life disposal issues, and recycling challenges.

4.2.3.2 Potential Solutions and Mitigation Strategies to be explored in the antimicrobial coatings case study

A range of potential solutions will be explored via the modelling tools to be implemented to address this case study. Examples include:

I. Development of Safe and Effective Alternatives:

- **Green Chemistry:** Research and develop antimicrobial agents based on green chemistry principles to minimise toxicity and environmental impact.
- **Bio-based Antimicrobials:** Use naturally derived antimicrobial agents that are biodegradable and less likely to cause resistance.
- **Harnessing UV light** for generating oxygen species or visible light for generating UV-C radiation (UV upconverters) which can provide permanent antimicrobial properties, directly or indirectly²⁴, on large-scale structures.

²⁴ Indirect antimicrobial effects can arise due to the UVC potentially activating quantum dots, that in turn will produce oxygen (and other) radicals that will kill bacteria.

2. Improved Formulations and Technologies:

- **Controlled Release Systems:** Develop coatings with controlled release mechanisms to extend efficacy and reduce the total amount of antimicrobial needed.
- **Nanoencapsulation:** Use nanoencapsulation to enhance the stability and efficacy of antimicrobial agents, minimising their environmental impact.
- **Stable and permanent antimicrobial coatings** that do not release ‘agents’ or loose efficacy over time as the antimicrobial function is an intrinsic part of the formulation itself.
- **Development of antimicrobial coatings where the functional properties are based on their physical effects** as the target organisms are hardly able to build resistance mechanisms (e.g. UVC, oxygen radical species via quantum dots,...).

3. Regulatory and Industry Collaboration:

- **Harmonised Standards:** Develop harmonised standards and guidelines for the use and testing of antimicrobial coatings to ensure safety and efficacy.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Foster collaboration between regulators, industry, and researchers to address safety and sustainability concerns comprehensively.

4. Enhanced Safety Protocols:

- **Worker Protection:** Implement strict safety protocols to protect workers from exposure during manufacturing and application.
- **Public Education:** Educate consumers and end-users about the proper use and disposal of antimicrobial-coated products to minimise risks.

By addressing these challenges through innovation, regulation, and collaboration, the safety and sustainability of antimicrobial coatings can be significantly improved.

4.2.3.3 Regulatory Landscape for the antimicrobial coatings case study

The regulatory landscape in Europe for antimicrobial coatings is complex and governed by several regulations and directives aimed at ensuring the safety, efficacy, and environmental impact of these products. Key regulations include the Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR), REACH, and various environmental and product-specific directives. Here is a detailed analysis:

I. Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR) (EU) No 528/2012

Scope and Purpose:

- **Scope:** The BPR regulates the placing on the market and use of biocidal products, including antimicrobial coatings, in the European Union.
- **Purpose:** Ensures a high level of protection for humans, animals, and the environment, while enhancing the functioning of the internal market through the harmonisation of regulations.

Key Provisions:

- **Authorization:** Manufacturers must obtain authorization for their antimicrobial coatings before they can be placed on the market. This involves submitting a dossier containing detailed information on the product's safety, efficacy, and environmental impact.
- **Active Substance Approval:** Active substances used in antimicrobial coatings must be approved by ECHA (European Chemicals Agency) before product authorization.
- **Labelling and Packaging:** Products must be appropriately labelled, providing information on safe use and potential hazards.

- Efficacy Testing: Antimicrobial coatings must undergo rigorous efficacy testing to demonstrate their effectiveness in reducing or eliminating microorganisms.

2. REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals) Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006

Scope and Purpose:

- Scope: Applies to the manufacture and import of chemical substances within the EU, including those used in antimicrobial coatings.
- Purpose: Ensures a high level of protection for human health and the environment through the comprehensive registration, evaluation, authorization, and restriction of chemicals.

Key Provisions:

- Registration: Chemical substances used in antimicrobial coatings must be registered with ECHA, providing detailed information on their properties and safe use.
- Evaluation: ECHA evaluates the submitted data to assess risks associated with the substance.
- Authorization: Certain substances may require authorization for specific uses if they are identified as substances of very high concern (SVHCs).
- Restriction: Some substances may be restricted or banned due to their hazardous properties.

3. CLP (Classification, Labelling, and Packaging) Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008

Scope and Purpose:

- Scope: Covers the classification, labelling, and packaging of substances and mixtures, including antimicrobial coatings.
- Purpose: Ensures that hazards presented by chemicals are clearly communicated to workers and consumers in the EU.

Key Provisions:

- Classification: Antimicrobial coatings must be classified according to their physical, health, and environmental hazards.
- Labelling: Products must carry labels with standardised symbols and phrases indicating the hazards and providing safety information.
- Packaging: Products must be packaged to ensure safe transport and handling.

4. Environmental and Product-Specific Directives

Environmental Impact:

- Waste Framework Directive (Directive 2008/98/EC): Regulates the management of waste, including waste containing antimicrobial substances, promoting recycling and proper disposal.
- Industrial Emissions Directive (Directive 2010/75/EU): Controls emissions from industrial installations producing antimicrobial coatings to minimise environmental impact.

Product-Specific Regulations:

- Construction Products Regulation (EU) No 305/2011: Covers the marketing of construction products, including antimicrobial coatings used in construction. Requires that products meet specific performance and safety criteria.
- Medical Devices Regulation (EU) 2017/745: Applies to antimicrobial coatings used on medical devices. These coatings must meet stringent safety and efficacy standards.

5. Standards and Testing

Harmonised Standards:

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- EN Standards: European Norms (EN) provide standardised methods for testing the efficacy, safety, and environmental impact of antimicrobial coatings.
- ISO Standards: International standards such as ISO 22196, which measures antibacterial activity on plastics and other non-porous surfaces, are often referenced.

The regulatory landscape for antimicrobial coatings in Europe is designed to ensure these products are safe, effective, and environmentally friendly. The Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR) is the primary regulatory framework, requiring rigorous testing and authorization of antimicrobial coatings. Complementary regulations such as REACH and CLP ensure comprehensive oversight of chemical substances used in these products. Additionally, various environmental and product-specific directives ensure that the production, use, and disposal of antimicrobial coatings do not pose undue risks to health or the environment. Compliance with these regulations and standards is essential for manufacturers and suppliers operating in the European market.

4.2.4 Per- and Polyfluorinated Substances (PFAS)

PFAS are a group of synthetic compounds used in various industrial and consumer applications, including fluoropolymers, textiles, and semiconductors. Despite covering thousands of diverse substances, all PFAS contain at least one fully fluorinated carbon atom chain. They are persistent in the environment and can be found in various matrices. Several individual PFAS have been identified as potential environmental pollutants and health hazards, with adverse effects related to development, the reproductive system, immune system suppression, and even cancer. However, the toxicity of PFAS can vary depending on the specific chemical and the route of exposure, and the effects of mixtures are largely unknown. From a socio-economic perspective, PFAS causes significant economic costs through burden on the healthcare system as well as the remediation of contaminated environments (Goldenman et al., 2019). Indirectly, the recognized health hazards also cause a variety of social concerns in affected communities, ranging from physical and mental health issues to financial uncertainty, stigmatisation, changes in land use and business opportunities, and lack of trust toward companies and government agencies (Banwell et al., 2021; Moeini et al., 2022; Menegatto & Zamperini, 2023).

Despite the known detrimental effects, PFAS are still widely used in industry. The global market size of PFAS was estimated to be around EUR 1.9 billion in 2019 and is expected to grow to EUR 2.5 billion by 2026, at a compound annual growth rate of 3.6% during the forecast period from 2021 to 2026. Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are used in many critical materials or components used in strategic industries such as avionics, electronics, Heating, Ventilation, Air Conditioning, and Refrigeration (HVAC-R), healthcare and medical device, and the chemical industry itself: lubricants, hydraulic fluids, coating, paints, adhesives, gaskets, seals, fittings and tubing, etc. due to their unique chemical and physical properties. These properties include high thermal stability, chemical resistance, low surface energy, and exceptional lubricity. PFAS are valued in these applications for their ability to perform under extreme conditions, including high temperatures, aggressive chemicals, and high pressures. Their stability and low reactivity make them suitable for a wide range of industries where traditional components may fail.

Some key applications of PFAS as lubricants include:

- I. Aerospace Industry:
 - High-Performance Aircraft Components: PFAS lubricants are used in critical aircraft components (e.g rotor mast) where extreme temperatures and harsh environments

- are common. They help ensure reliable operation and reduce friction and wear in parts such as bearings, gears, and actuators.
- Seals and Gaskets: They are also applied to seals and gaskets to reduce friction and prevent leaks, contributing to the overall efficiency and durability of automotive components.
 - The avionic industry declares that no alternatives to PFAS are nowadays available.
2. **Automotive Industry:**
 - Engine and Transmission Systems: PFAS-based lubricants are used in engines and transmission systems to provide superior lubrication under high temperatures and pressures, enhancing performance and longevity.
 3. **Electronics and Electrical Equipment:**
 - Connector Lubrication: PFAS lubricants are used in electrical connectors to reduce wear and corrosion, ensuring reliable electrical connections over extended periods. Additionally, PFAS lubricants are non-flammable, making them suitable for use in environments where fire safety is a concern.
 - Cooling Systems: They are used in the cooling systems of electronic devices to manage heat and ensure efficient operation.
 4. **Industrial Machinery:**
 - Heavy Machinery and Equipment: PFAS lubricants are used in heavy machinery to reduce friction and wear in components such as bearings, gears, and hydraulic systems, particularly in environments with high temperatures and aggressive chemicals.
 - Metalworking: They are used as coolants and lubricants in metalworking processes, such as cutting, grinding, and forming, to improve the precision and quality of the finished products.
 5. **Medical Devices:**
 - Precision Instruments: PFAS lubricants are used in medical instruments and devices that require high precision and reliability. They ensure smooth operation and reduce the risk of wear and tear.
 - Surgical Tools: These lubricants are applied to surgical tools and devices to enhance their performance and longevity, especially those exposed to sterilization processes.
 6. **Food Processing:**
 - Food-Grade Lubricants: PFAS-based lubricants that meet food-grade standards are used in food processing equipment to reduce friction and wear, ensuring efficient operation without compromising food safety.
 7. **Textiles:**
 - Sewing and Weaving: In textile manufacturing, PFAS lubricants are used to reduce friction in sewing and weaving machines, improving the efficiency and lifespan of the equipment.
 8. **Marine Industry:**
 - Marine Engines and Equipment: PFAS lubricants are applied to marine engines and equipment to withstand harsh marine environments, providing reliable lubrication and protection against corrosion.
 9. **Optical and Photographic Equipment:**
 - Lens and Shutter Mechanisms: PFAS lubricants are used in cameras and optical instruments to ensure smooth operation of lens and shutter mechanisms, enhancing performance and durability.
 10. **Paper and Pulp Industry:**
 - Processing Equipment: They are used in paper and pulp processing equipment to reduce friction and wear, improving efficiency and extending the lifespan of the machinery.

Table 5 provides a comprehensive overview of the various challenges associated with the production and application of PFAS, highlighting environmental, health, economic, performance, sustainability, and regulatory issues.

Table 5. Summary of Problems with Safety and Sustainability of PFAS

Issue	Description
Human Health Concerns	PFAS exposure is linked to a variety of health issues, including developmental problems, reproductive system toxicity, immune system suppression, and cancer.
Environmental Impact	PFAS are persistent in the environment, bioaccumulate in wildlife and humans, and exhibit ecotoxicity. They can disrupt ecosystems and microbial communities due to their long-lasting nature and mobility in water.
Economic Issues	The production and remediation of PFAS-contaminated sites incur high costs. Additionally, managing health impacts related to PFAS exposure places a significant financial burden on healthcare systems which is currently not evaluable.
Regulatory Challenges	PFAS face stringent regulations due to their toxicity and persistence. Compliance with current legislation and forthcoming ones requires substantial resources and coordination among industries and regulatory bodies. The policy gap is still debated.
Sustainability Concerns	PFAS production relies on non-renewable resources and they pose end-of-life disposal challenges as they are not easily degradable, complicating recycling and leading to long-term environmental contamination.

4.2.4.1 Comprehensive Data Gathering and Assessment on PFAS

The INSIGHT project aims to gather and assess a broad spectrum of data related to the economic impact, life cycle, and toxicity of PFAS, including detailed toxicogenomic data. This information will be sourced from specialized literature, public sources such as government and supranational agency reports, and parallel EU-funded projects expected to release publicly available data soon. Examples of such projects include [SCENARIOS](#)²⁵, and through collaboration with concurrent projects [CHIASMA](#)²⁶, and [PINK](#)²⁷, which are participated by some of the INSIGHT partners. Additionally, collaboration with SCENARIOS' sister project [PROMISCES](#)²⁸ is also foreseen. By integrating diverse data sources and leveraging advanced integrated models, INSIGHT will provide a robust understanding of PFAS impacts, aiding in better decision-making for human health and environmental protection

Data Sources and Data Collection

Economic Impact:

INSIGHT will collect economic data to evaluate the financial implications of PFAS on various industries and communities focusing on the specific case studies of the aerospace industry. This will include:

²⁵ SCENARIOS project: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101037509>

²⁶ CHIASMA project: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101137613>

²⁷ PINK project: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101137809>

²⁸ PROMICES project: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036449>

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- **Healthcare Costs:** Expenses related to the treatment of PFAS-related illnesses.
- **Environmental Remediation:** Costs associated with cleaning up PFAS-contaminated sites.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** Financial burden of adhering to PFAS regulations.

Life Cycle Analysis (LCA):

The project will conduct a comprehensive life cycle analysis of PFAS, tracing their journey from production to disposal. This will involve:

- **Resource and Energy Consumption:** Evaluating the resources and energy used at each stage of the PFAS life cycle.
- **Environmental Impact:** Assessing the environmental footprint of PFAS production, use, and disposal.

Toxicity Assessment

INSIGHT will assess the toxicity of PFAS using data from various sources, focusing on:

- **Toxicity Studies:** Data from animal and in vitro studies on PFAS effects.
- **Toxicogenomics:** Data on how PFAS affects gene expression, providing insights into molecular mechanisms of toxicity.
- **Epidemiological Studies:** Research on health outcomes in populations exposed to PFAS.

4.2.4.2 Goals and Expected Outcomes of the PFAS case study

The comprehensive data gathered and analyzed by INSIGHT will support:

- **Industry Practices:** Guiding industries towards safer and more sustainable practices concerning PFAS, including the use of alternative products.
- **Public Awareness:** Educating the public about the risks of PFAS and measures to reduce exposure.
- **Policy Development:** Informing policymakers to create effective regulations for managing PFAS risks.

4.2.4.3 Regulatory Landscape for the PFAS case study

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a group of man-made chemicals that have been widely used in various industrial applications, including as lubricants. The European Union (EU) has established a regulatory framework to manage the use and environmental impact of PFAS due to their persistence, bioaccumulation potential, and associated health risks. Here are the key EU regulations relevant to the use of PFAS as lubricants:

- I. REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals) Regulation (EC 1907/2006):
 - Registration and Evaluation: Companies manufacturing or importing PFAS in quantities of one tonne or more per year must register these substances with the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA). Registration involves providing data on the properties, uses, and safe handling of the chemicals.
 - Authorisation: Certain PFAS may require authorisation for specific uses if they are identified as substances of very high concern (SVHCs). This process ensures that such substances are progressively replaced by suitable alternatives.

- Restriction: The use of some PFAS may be restricted under REACH Annex XVII. Restrictions can limit the manufacture, placing on the market, or use of specific PFAS or products containing them.
- 2. Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) Regulation (EU 2019/1021):
 - Elimination and Reduction: This regulation aims to eliminate or restrict the production and use of persistent organic pollutants. Certain PFAS, such as perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and its salts, are listed in the regulation and are subject to stringent control measures.
- 3. CLP (Classification, Labelling and Packaging) Regulation (EC 1272/2008):
 - Hazard Communication: PFAS used as lubricants must be classified and labelled according to their hazardous properties. This includes providing information on physical, health, and environmental hazards to ensure safe handling and use.
- 4. Waste Framework Directive (Directive 2008/98/EC):
 - Waste Management: The directive sets the legal framework for treating and managing waste in the EU. Producers and users of PFAS-containing lubricants must ensure proper waste management practices to minimise environmental contamination and promote recycling and safe disposal.
- 5. Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC) and Groundwater Directive (Directive 2006/118/EC):
 - Water Quality Standards: These directives set standards for maintaining and improving the quality of water bodies in the EU. PFAS are considered priority substances, and their discharge into water bodies is regulated to protect aquatic environments and human health.
- 6. Industrial Emissions Directive (Directive 2010/75/EU):
 - Emission Control: Regulates the release of pollutants from industrial installations, including those using PFAS. Facilities using PFAS as lubricants must obtain permits and implement measures to control emissions and minimise environmental impact.
- 7. Drinking Water Directive (Directive 2020/2184/EU):
 - Safe Drinking Water: Sets quality standards for drinking water, including limits for certain PFAS. This impacts the permissible levels of PFAS contamination in water supplies, indirectly influencing their use in various applications.
- 8. Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) Directive (Directive 2008/105/EC):
 - Surface Water Protection: Establishes environmental quality standards for priority substances, including certain PFAS, to protect surface water quality.

In summary, the EU regulatory environment for PFAS used as lubricants is comprehensive, encompassing various regulations aimed at ensuring chemical safety, environmental protection, and public health. Compliance with these regulations is essential for companies manufacturing, using, or handling PFAS-based lubricants within the EU.

4.3 Partner engagement in and support for case study development

Given the central role of the case studies in demonstrating the utility and regulatory benefits of the INSIGHT *in silico* framework and integrated chemo- and nano-informatics tools, INSIGHT has defined and formalized roles for all INSIGHT partners to support the development and delivery of the case studies, as shown schematically in Figure 6. The Case study leads provide the overall direction for the case studies, and one industry and one academic lead partner has been assigned to each case study. The modelling and infrastructure partners are central to the technical delivery of the case studies, developing, integrating and aligning the modelling resources, application programming interface (APIs) and graphical user interfaces (GUIs) for user interaction with the various tools and workflows. All INSIGHT partners will support with data curation, documentation of the models and workflows into user-friendly step-by-step processes, including beta-testing the workflows as non-technical experts, and promoting and disseminating the INSIGHT *in silico* framework and the case studies.

Figure 6. Summary of the roles and contributions of all INSIGHT partners to the development, implementation and dissemination of INSIGHT case studies. Each case study has a lead industry and academic partner, a core set of modelling and infrastructure providing partners, and a set of support partners who provide guidance on the regulatory landscape, dissemination approaches, documentation of the case studies and so forth.

4.4 Key performance indicators for the INSIGHT Case Studies

Internal evaluation of the INSIGHT Case Studies, and decisions as to which ones will be developed and fully documented, this document suggests some potential Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for each of the Case Studies, in the context of addressing regulatory gaps, risk assessment and mitigation, promoting sustainable alternatives, enhancing regulatory effectiveness, stakeholder engagement and collaboration, and long-term sustainability concerning PFAS, advanced materials, and antimicrobial surfaces.

It is essential to underscore that the primary indicator of INSIGHT's success will be the number and quality of models successfully integrated for the implementation of the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) procedure for each case study. Furthermore, we envisage to gather and assess the SSbD performance according to the following possible indicators:

Addressing Regulatory Gaps:

I. Number of Identified Regulatory Gaps which INSIGHT can cover:

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- Quantitative and qualitative analysis of regulations on PFAS, advanced materials, and antimicrobial surfaces. % of materials which are not adequately addressed.

2. Gap Closure Rate due to INSIGHT

- Percentage of identified regulatory gaps that are addressed through policy revisions or new regulations.

Risk Assessment and Mitigation:

1. Risk Assessment Completion Rate:

- Percentage of PFAS, advanced carbon materials, and antimicrobial surfaces subjected to comprehensive risk assessments in INSIGHT (many data will be available from sister projects)

2. Mitigation Implementation Rate:

- Percentage of identified risks associated with PFAS, advanced carbon materials, and antimicrobial surfaces for which mitigation measures are suggested / implemented.

Promoting Sustainable Alternatives:

1. Number of Sustainable Alternatives Identified:

- Count of alternative materials or practices identified as substitutes for PFAS (CSI), and if relevant to advanced carbon materials, and (nano-)pesticides.

2. Adoption Rate of Sustainable Alternatives:

- Percentage increase in the adoption of identified sustainable alternatives over time (difficult considered the duration of the project, but it's possible to force in the CSs, e.g. swapping a toxic pesticide with a less toxic one).

Enhancing Regulatory Effectiveness:

1. Regulatory Compliance Rate:

- Percentage of industries and stakeholders complying with updated regulations regarding PFAS, advanced carbon materials, and antimicrobial surfaces.

2. Enforcement Efficiency:

- Time taken to address non-compliance issues related to PFAS, advanced carbon materials, and antimicrobial surfaces.

Stakeholder Engagement and Collaboration:

1. Stakeholder Participation Rate:

- Percentage of relevant stakeholders actively engaged in discussions, workshops, or policy development regarding PFAS, advanced carbon materials, and antimicrobial surfaces.

2. Collaborative Initiatives Developed:

- Number of collaborative projects or initiatives established among stakeholders to address regulatory gaps or promote sustainable practices.

Long-term Sustainability:

1. Reduction in Environmental Impact:

- Percentage reduction in the environmental footprint associated with PFAS and pesticides over a specified period. Graphenes: safe by design?

2. Public Awareness and Education:

- Increase in public awareness (No. people touched) and understanding of the risks associated with PFAS, advanced carbon materials, and antimicrobial surfaces (No. of public seminars), measured through surveys or outreach programs.

5 Use of the INSIGHT R&I Strategy throughout the project

5.1 Summary of key decisions taken to date

Leads for Case Studies

The INSIGHT project has identified and appointed both industry and academic leads for all case studies. These leads are responsible for guiding the progression of each case study, ensuring that all activities remain on track and align with the project's goals. The involvement of both industry and academic leaders ensures a balanced perspective, leveraging practical industrial experience and cutting-edge academic research to drive the case studies forward.

Criteria for Go/No Go Decisions

Criteria for making Go/No Go decisions for the case studies have been established. These criteria will be implemented to evaluate the progress and viability of each case study. A critical review is scheduled for month 18 of the project, at which point the performance and outcomes of the case studies will be assessed. This review will determine which case studies will continue to full documentation as stand-alone deliverables. Successful case studies will advance to the final stages, corresponding to Milestones 7 and 8 (for Case Study 1 and 2, respectively) and Deliverable DI.4, which encompasses the complete documentation of the case studies. Further elaboration of the Go/No GO criteria will be developed over the next 6 months, and discussed and agreed with the Case study leads, the external advisory board prior to their implementation.

Key Performance Indicators

The key performance indicators (KPIs) for the INSIGHT project will primarily focus on the integration and demonstration of new insights derived from integrating various modeling approaches. These KPIs are designed to measure the effectiveness of the integrated models in providing comprehensive and actionable insights into the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) procedure applied to each case study.

Use of Nanopublications

To ensure thorough documentation and integration of metadata into the INSIGHT Knowledge Graph, nanopublications will be utilized to record the case studies, including the datasets underpinning them and the associated metadata. Nanopublications provide a structured and standardized format for documenting scientific data, making it easier to share and integrate into larger knowledge frameworks. This approach will ensure that all relevant information is accessible, machine-actionable and re-usable for future research and decision-making. Further details on this process are described in Section 5.2 below.

5.2 Alignment with the INSIGHT Data Management Plan

The INSIGHT data management plan builds on the expertise that was developed in [NanoCommons](#)²⁹, [NanoSolveIT](#)³⁰, [WorldFAIR](#)³¹, [PARC](#)³² and other projects addressing specifically informatics and data harmonisation. As the INSIGHT case studies are one of the largest outputs from INSIGHT, and combine curated experimental data and multiple computational approaches in which the input and output data formats must be aligned, management of the case study data forms a core aspect of the INSIGHT DMP. A key focus of the INSIGHT DMP, and of the INSIGHT case studies, is ensuring not just FAIR data and models/software but full *machine-actionability* of the case studies. Machine-Actionability refers to the information that is consistently structured so that machines can be programmed against such a structure.

An emerging approach to provide this consistent structure, that is fully aligned with the concept and implementation of Knowledge Graphs (which form the basis of the INSIGHT in silico framework) is that of nanopublications. Nanopublications are the smallest units of publishable information: a scientifically meaningful assertion about anything that can be uniquely identified and attributed to its author and serve to communicate a **single statement**, its **original source** (provenance) and **citation record** (publication info), as shown schematically in Figure 7. Nanopublications are thus a concept designed to facilitate the structured and precise sharing of scientific assertions, making them an integral component of knowledge graphs.

Definition of Nanopublications

A nanopublication is a minimal, machine-readable representation of a scientific assertion, enriched with provenance and publication metadata. It typically includes:

- **Assertion:** The core statement or claim, such as a scientific fact or relationship.
- **Provenance:** Metadata detailing the origin and context of the assertion, including who made it, when, and under what circumstances.
- **Publication Info:** Metadata about the nanopublication itself, such as its creator, publication date, and version.

Structure of Nanopublications

A nanopublication is generally structured into three main parts:

- **Assertion (rdf):** This part contains the primary claim or statement, usually represented in RDF (Resource Description Framework) format. For example, "Gene X is associated with Disease Y."
- **Provenance (rdf):** This part includes details about the evidence supporting the assertion, the methods used to derive it, and references to the original sources or datasets.
- **Publication Info (rdf):** This part provides metadata about the nanopublication itself, such as the authors, creation date, and version history.

Integration of nanopublications into Knowledge Graphs

Nanopublications fit seamlessly into knowledge graphs due to their structured, RDF-based format, which is compatible with the principles of Linked Data and the Semantic Web.

²⁹ NanoCommons: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/731032>

³⁰ NanoSolveIT: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/814572>

³¹ WorldFAIR: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058393>

³² PARC: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101057014>


```

sub:head {
  this: np:hasAssertion sub:assertion ;
  np:hasProvenance sub:provenance ;
  np:hasPublicationInfo sub:publicationInfo ;
  a np:Nanopublication .
}

sub:assertion {
  dgn-gda:DCNc2b5d698480ad1c4ab7a2b530b1ae5c sio:SIO_000628 miriam-gene:92 , lld:C133990 ;
  a sio:SIO_001121 .
}

sub:provenance {
  sub:assertion dcterm:description "[S-ASA increases replication fidelity in mononucleotide, dinucleotide, and tetranucleotide repeats and reduces mutations in tumor suppressor genes TGFBR2 and ACVR2, a finding that may provoke in vivo studies for the prevention of colorectal cancer in hereditary nonpolyposis colorectal cancer.]. Sentence from MEDLINE/PubMed, a database of the U.S. National Library of Medicine."@en ;
  wi:evidence dgn-void:source_evidence_literature ;
  sio:SIO_000772 miriam-pubmed:20197483 ;
  prov:wasDerivedFrom dgn-void:BEFREE ;
  prov:wasGeneratedBy eco:ECO_0000203 ;
  dgn-void:BEFREE pav:importedOn "2017-02-19"^^xsd:date .
  dgn-void:source_evidence_literature a eco:ECO_0000212 ;
  rdfs:comment "Gene-disease associations inferred from text-mining the literature."@en ;
  rdfs:label "DisGeNET evidence - LITERATURE"@en .
}

sub:publicationInfo {
  this: dcterm:created "2017-10-17T13:10:15+02:00"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  dcterm:rights <http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0/> ;
  dcterm:rightsHolder dgn-void:IBIGroup ;
  dcterm:subject sio:SIO_000983 ;
  prv:useData dgn-void:disgenetv3.0rdf ;
  pav:authoredBy <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-5999-6269> , <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-7534-7661> ,
  <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-9383-528x> , <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-0169-8159> , <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-1244-7654> ;
  pav:createdBy <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-0169-8159> ;
  pav:version "v5.0.0.0" ;
  dgn-void:disgenetv3.0rdf pav:version "v5.0.0" .
}

```


A RDF serialization of a nanopublication

B Graphical view of the nanopublication

C A network of gene-disease associations

Figure 7: Nanopublications explained. (A) RDF (trig) representation of the nanopublication encoding an assertion: (activin A receptor type 2A—gene—disease association—Colorectal Cancer); (B) graphical representation of the four parts of the nanopublications with a human-readable representation of the assertion graph; (C) network of gene-disease associations created by five nanopublications. Reproduced from Giachelle et al. (2021).

RDF and Triples:

- **Basic Unit:** Like knowledge graphs, nanopublications use RDF triples (subject-predicate-object) to represent information. This allows them to be easily incorporated into existing knowledge graphs, where each triple contributes to the overall network of information.
- **Interlinking:** Nanopublications can link to other RDF resources within a knowledge graph, establishing relationships and contextual connections. For example, a nanopublication about a gene-disease association can link to other entities representing genes, diseases, or research articles.

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Provenance and Trust:

- **Transparency:** The inclusion of provenance metadata enhances the transparency and trustworthiness of the assertions in the knowledge graph. Users can trace the origin and evidence of each assertion, which is crucial for scientific data.
- **Credibility:** By providing detailed provenance, nanopublications help in assessing the credibility and reliability of the data within the knowledge graph.

Query and Inference:

- **SPARQL Queries:** Knowledge graphs can be queried using SPARQL (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language). Nanopublications, being part of the RDF structure, can be queried to retrieve specific assertions, their provenance, and publication information.
- **Reasoning:** The structured format of nanopublications supports automated reasoning and inference. For example, if multiple nanopublications provide evidence for a particular relationship, this can be used to strengthen the overall confidence in that relationship within the knowledge graph.

Applications and Benefits of nanopublications

Data Integration:

- **Interoperability:** Nanopublications enable interoperability between different datasets and knowledge graphs, as they adhere to standard RDF formats.
- **Aggregation:** They facilitate the aggregation of data from multiple sources, enriching the knowledge graph with diverse and comprehensive information.

Scientific Communication:

- **Precision:** Nanopublications allow precise communication of scientific findings, ensuring that complex assertions are accurately represented and understood.
- **Reuse:** Researchers can reuse nanopublications in different contexts, integrating them into new studies and analyses.

Enhanced Discovery:

- **Linked Data:** The interlinked nature of nanopublications within a knowledge graph enhances data discovery and retrieval, allowing users to navigate through related information efficiently.
- **Automated Analysis:** Automated tools can analyze nanopublications to identify patterns, trends, and new insights, contributing to scientific advancements.

Nanopublications thus serve as modular, precise units of knowledge within knowledge graphs, encapsulating scientific assertions along with their provenance and publication metadata. Their RDF-based structure ensures compatibility with knowledge graphs, facilitating integration, query, and inference. By enhancing transparency, credibility, and interoperability, nanopublications play a crucial role in advancing data-driven scientific research and knowledge sharing.

INSIGHT will define a series of nanopublication templates to describe the key relationships between the case study materials, their research questions, the models utilised, and the toxicological and sustainability criteria identified. The case studies will then be documented as collections of nanopublications that contain all of the necessary metadata and define the nodes and edges of the Knowledge Graph underpinning the INSIGHT in silico framework for SSbD of materials and chemicals.

5.3 Next steps and documentation of Case Studies via nanopublications

The INSIGHT Case studies will serve as focal points for project communications, and as a monitoring tool helping to define the progress towards model integration and innovation, with checkpoint on

progress towards the case studies built into the WPI activities for the project duration. The benchmarks of success, or the Key Performance Indicators as outlined in draft form in this deliverable, will be further refined together with the WP leaders, noting again that the success of the case studies is determined based on their demonstration of the ability to usefully link and integrate models, and to use these integrated models to provide more holistic insights into the safety and sustainability of the case study chemicals and materials. All other WPs feed into the delivery of the case studies, and as such WPI has the role of integrating, consolidating, and organising the INSIGHT advances around the case studies to demonstrate impact.

With the successful elaboration of the INSIGHT Case studies the project partners are well positioned to achieve the planned model integration and demonstration activities of INSIGHT. As a living document, the case study planning documents, including the excel sheets collating the data, keywords for the knowledge graph, and the planning timelines will be adapted and changed, if applicable.

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ANNEX AI – Social Impact Factors and Indicators

Social impact categories & indicators - synthesis					
Stakeholder	Impact category / social area	Subcategory / social topic	Indicators	Data source examples	Reference examples
WORKER	WORKING CONDITIONS	Freedom of association	Freedom of association rights	Country/sector data from databases: PSILCA, SHDB, Soca	Teah & Onuki (2017); Vidaurre et al. (2022); Tsalidis et al. (2023); Muller et al. (2021)
	WORKING CONDITIONS	Fair salary	Average wage	Site-specific (can be compared to sectoral/country averages)	Siebert et al. (2018); Furtner et al. (2021); Souza et al. (2016); Muller et al. (2021); Souza et al. (2021)
	WORKING CONDITIONS	Working hours	(Effective) working hours Excessive working time Overtime compensation	Site-specific, databases: PSILCA Database: SHDB, generic data sources: US Department of State -	UNEP (2021); Furtner et al. (2021); Siebert et al. (2018); Muller et al. (2021); Tsalidis et al. (2023) Valente et al. (2017); Pucciarelli et al. (2021); Teah & Onuki (2017); Orola et al. (2022); Stoycheva et al. (2022) Siebert et al. 2018; Furtner et al. 2021
	WORKING CONDITIONS / HUMAN RIGHTS	Child labor	Number / percentage of children in labor	Databases: PSILCA, Soca, SHDB (risk levels), generic data sources: ILOSTAT, Specific statistics - Bureau of International Labor Affairs (2018), ILO, US Department of Labor, UNICEF, site-specific data.	UNEP (2021); Muller et al. (2021); Tsalidis et al. (2023); Vidaurre et al. (2022); Foolmaun & Ramjeeawon (2013); Teah & Onuki (2017); Furtner et al. (2021); Orola et al. (2022); Stoycheva et al. (2022); Subramanian et al. (2018)
	WORKING CONDITIONS / HUMAN RIGHTS	Forced labor	Use / frequency / prevalence of forced labor	Databases: PSILCA, Soca, SHDB (risk levels), generic data sources: ILO, U.S.A Department of Labor 2020.	Hosseiniyou et al. (2014); Tsalidis et al. (2023); Iribarren et al. (2022); Teah & Onuki (2017); Vidaurre et al. (2022); Stoycheva et al. (2022); Furtner et al. (2021)
	WORKING CONDITIONS / HUMAN RIGHTS	Equal opportunities / discrimination	Rate of women in labor force Gender wage gap Incidents of discrimination	Databases: PSILCA Databases: PSILCA, Soca, generic data sources: ILO Databases: SHDB	Souza et al. (2016); Tsalidis et al. (2023); Iribarren et al. (2022); Furtner et al. (2021) UNEP (2021); GRI400; Vidaurre et al. (2022); Tsalidis et al. (2023) UNEP (2021); GRI400; Stoycheva et al. (2022); Pucciarelli et al. (2021); Hosseiniyou et al. (2014)
	HEALTH AND SAFETY	Health and safety	Occupational accidents (non-fatal) Occupational accidents (fatal) Occupational diseases Occupational toxics and hazards Adequate occupational safety measures Use of protective equipment Emergency protocols for accidents	Databases: PSILCA, Soca, SHDB, generic data sources: ILOSTAT, Eurostat, Hämeälinen et al. 2006 & 2009, site-specific data. Databases: PSILCA, Soca, generic data sources: ILOSTAT, Eurostat, site-specific data Site-specific data Site-specific data Site-specific data	UNEP (2021); GRI 400; Furtner et al. (2021); Siebert et al. (2018); Souza et al. (2016); Hosseiniyou et al. (2014); Orola et al. (2022); Stoycheva et al. (2022); Souza et al. (2021); Foolmaun & Ramjeeawon (2013); Vidaurre et al. (2022); Tsalidis et al. (2023); Muller et al. (2021); Teah & Onuki (2017); Valente et al. (2017); Pucciarelli et al. (2021); Subramanian et al. (2018) UNEP (2021); Siebert et al. (2018); Teah & Onuki (2017); Muller et al. (2021); Vidaurre et al. (2022); Tsalidis et al. (2023) Orola et al. (2022); Pucciarelli et al. (2021); GRI 400 Stoycheva et al. 2022; Pucciarelli et al. 2021; Valente et al. 2017; Furtner et al. 2021 UNEP (2021); Muller et al. (2021); Tsalidis et al. (2023) UNEP (2021); Foolmaun & Ramjeeawon 2013 UNEP (2021); Foolmaun & Ramjeeawon 2013
	SKILLS AND KNOWLEDGE	Skills and knowledge	Professional training (days/hours) Employees participated in training Percentage of trainees of all employees	Company reports Site-specific data Site-specific data	Subramanian et al. 2018; GRI 400 Siebert et al. 2018 Siebert et al. 2018

LOCAL COMMUNITY	HEALTH AND SAFETY	Safe and healthy living conditions	Sanitation coverage	Databases: PSILCA, SHDB, Soca, generic data sources: WHO	Muller et al. (2021); Vidaurre et al. (2022); Tsalidis et al. (2023); Stoycheva et al. (2022); Pucciarelli et al. (2021)
			Drinking water coverage	Databases: PSILCA, SHDB, Soca, generic data sources: JMP	Muller et al. (2021); Vidaurre et al. (2022); Tsalidis et al. (2023); Stoycheva et al. (2022); Pucciarelli et al. (2021)
			Pollution levels	Databases: PSILCA	Hosseiniyou et al. (2014); Tsalidis et al. (2023); Furtner et al. (2021)
			Generation of waste / hazards Management effort to minimize use of hazardous substances Psychological health effects	Site-specific Site-specific, generic data sources: Ecolex Site-specific	Hosseiniyou et al. 2014; Muller et al. 2021 UNEP (2021); Furtner et al. 2021 Banwell et al. 2021; Menegatto & Zamperini 2023
	HUMAN RIGHTS / CULTURAL HERITAGE	Access to material resources	Level of industrial water use	Databases: PSILCA, Soca	Hosseiniyou et al. (2014); Vidaurre et al. (2022); Tsalidis et al. (2023)
			Extraction of material resources (biomass/fossil fuels/minerals/ores) Certified environmental management system	Databases: PSILCA, Soca Site-specific	Hosseiniyou et al. (2014); Vidaurre et al. (2022); Tsalidis et al. (2023) UNEP (2021); Stoycheva et al. 2022; Tsalidis et al. 2023; Muller et al. 2021
	HUMAN RIGHTS / CULTURAL HERITAGE	Respect of indigenous rights	Presence of indigenous populations	Databases: PSILCA, Soca, generic data sources: Minority rights group international 2020	Vidaurre et al. 2022; Tsalidis et al. 2023; Muller et al. 2021
	HUMAN RIGHTS / CULTURAL HERITAGE / WORKING CONDITIONS	Delocalization and migration	International migrant stock	Databases: PSILCA, Soca, generic data sources: UN DESA	Vidaurre et al. 2022; Tsalidis et al. 2023; Muller et al. 2021
			Net migration rate	Databases: PSILCA, Soca, generic data sources: CIA Site-specific, generic data sources: UNESCO, U.S. Department of State Country Reports on Human rights Practices	Vidaurre et al. 2022; Tsalidis et al. 2023; Muller et al. 2021 UNEP (2021); Hosseiniyou et al. (2014); Furtner et al. (2021)
	CULTURAL HERITAGE	Cultural heritage	Policies for the protection of cultural heritage	Databases: PSILCA, SHDB, Soca, generic data sources: ILOSTAT	Muller et al. (2021); Vidaurre et al. (2021); Tsalidis et al. (2023); Furtner et al. (2021); Stoycheva et al. (2022)
SOSIO-ECONOMIC REPERCUSSIONS	Local employment	Unemployment rate in country	Databases: PSILCA, generic data sources: ILO	Siebert et al. (2018); Hosseiniyou et al. (2014); Singh & Gupta (2017); Furtner et al. (2021)	
Number of local jobs created					
VALUE CHAIN ACTORS	GOVERNANCE	Promoting social responsibility	Membership in an initiative that promotes social responsibility along the supply chain	Site-specific	UNEP (2021); Tsalidis et al. 2023
			Organizations' involvement in corruption (in value chain)		Tsalidis et al. 2023; Muller et al. 2021
			Selecting suppliers from corruption-free areas		Stoycheva et al. 2022
HUMAN RIGHTS	Prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts	Conflict-free operations to reduce and prevent conflicts when supplier operates in conflict zone		Stoycheva et al. 2022	
CONSUMER	HEALTH AND SAFETY	Health and safety	Procedures to assess consumer health and safety	Site-specific	UNEP (2021); GRI 400; Stoycheva et al. 2022
			Product impact on consumer		Stoycheva et al. 2022

SOCIETY	SOSIO-ECONOMIC REPERCUSSIONS	Contribution to economic development	Contribution of the product/service/organization/sector to economic development (e.g., annual growth)	Database for sectoral data: PSILCA	UNEP (2021); Stoycheva et al. (2022); Hosseinijou et al. (2014); Iribarren et al. (2022); Tsalidis et al. (2023); Muller et al. (2021)
		Education	Illiteracy rate	Database: PSILCA, Soca, generic data sources: UNESCO	Muller et al. 2021; Vidaurre et al. 2022; Tsalidis et al. 2023
	SOSIO-ECONOMIC REPERCUSSIONS	Technology development	Partnerships in research and development Expenditure in research and development	Site-specific Generic data sources: OECD	UNEP (2021); Stoycheva et al. 2022; Furtner et al. 2021 Subramanian et al. 2018
	GOVERNANCE	Corruption	Measures for the prevention of corruption Organization's involvement in corruption / incidents of corruption	Site-specific	UNEP (2021); Furtner et al. (2021); Stoycheva et al. (2022); GRI 200
			Risk of corruption (country/region)	Site-specific Generic data sources: Transparency International, World Economic Forum	UNEP (2021); Stoycheva et al. (2022); Singh & Gupta (2017)
			Public sector corruption	Databases: PSILCA, Soca, generic data sources: Transparency International	Teah & Onuki (2017); Pucciarelli et al. (2021); Furtner et al. (2021) Tsalidis et al. (2023); Vidaurre et al. (2022); Muller et al. (2021)
	HUMAN RIGHTS	Prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts	Conflict-free operations to reduce and prevent conflicts when organization operates in a conflict zone		Stoycheva et al. 2022